

Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 15 to 23

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The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19410>

Abstract

*This work bring different ways of representing prime magic squares. These are of type: **blocks, block-bordered, concentric, nested**, etc. This work is for the orders 15 to 23 with prime number entries. For previous work from orders 6 to 14 refer [9]. There are magic squares such as of orders 17, 19, 22, 23, etc. These are either prime number orders or double-prime number orders. There is a difficulty in representing them in equal sums blocks. In case of orders 22, we are able bring blocks of equal sums of order 11 with prime numbers. In case of 17, 19 and 23, a little different approach is applied. For these types of magic squares, an external borders are considered, and the internal part is represented in terms of blocks, for example, in case of orders 17, 19 and 23, blocks of order 15 and 21 are applied in the inner parts.*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260	260
260	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9	pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc										369
31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11	369	
30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16	369	
35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15	369	
22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56	369	
21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61	369	
26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60	369	
67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47	369	
66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52	369	
71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51	369	
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums.

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10	mgc										505
91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505	
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88	505	
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505	
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505	
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505	
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505	
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505	
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505	
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505	
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 10.

2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

2.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• **Blocks of Order 3**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• **Blocks of Order 4**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• Blocks of Order 6

12	mgc												870
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author’s work [26, 27, 28].

Based on the idea of **blocks**, **block-borders**, etc. given above, we shall concentrate our work in this direction for **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts. This is second part for the orders 15 to 23. The first part is for the orders 6 to 14.

3 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Order 15-23

This work brings different ways representing magic squares in prime numbers. Initial aim is represent in terms of blocks. Some of possibilities led us to concentric or single-layer bordered magic squares. It includes blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, etc. Sometimes these blocks are of **equal** or **different** magic sums. This work is for the orders 15 to 23. In case of order 17, 19 and 23, we don’t have division in blocks but we represent them as block-bordered. This means there are one or two layers of border, while the internal part is as blocks of small orders.

Whenever, we write **prime magic square**, it means that the magic squares are composed of **distinct prime number entries**, except in few cases, we the central constant 1000003 is repeating. This constant generally goes up to certain

order,i.e, around order 120. For orders higher than this, the next central constant is used. It is only in case of odd order primes magic squares.

For each order we worked with **different types of representations** of prime magic squares. Below is the list in each case.

Order	Representations
15	5
16	4
17	5
18	6
19	5
20	7
21	5
22	8
23	5
Total	50

This work is specially for distinct prime numbers, except in some cases there are repetition of central values. For similar kind of work for sequential numbers entries, see the author's work [21, 26, 27, 28] given in the reference list.

3.1 Prime Magic Squares of Order 15

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 15 with different representations.

Example 1. *Different Sums Blocks of Order 3.* Let's consider a following prime magic square:

15	mgc															31500045	
		1597397	1291163	2114771	1754497	2407549	3894523	1075241	2140847	2704469	1113221	1616597	2631029	1961537	2714111	2483093	31500045
		2185151	1667777	1150403	4825549	2685523	545497	3602747	1973519	344291	3304757	1786949	269141	2907803	2386247	1864691	31500045
		1220783	2044391	1738157	1476523	2963497	3616549	1242569	1806191	2871797	942869	1957301	2460677	2289401	2058383	2810957	31500045
		1666081	1143049	2203153	1762477	2285683	3158791	1462999	1012831	2228167	1709671	2380387	3192439	2317067	1868561	3108689	31500045
		2207833	1670761	1133689	3798631	2402317	1006003	2333167	1567999	802831	3910267	2427499	944731	3223061	2431439	1639817	31500045
		1138369	2198473	1675441	1645843	2518951	3042157	907831	2123167	1672999	1662559	2474611	3145327	1754189	2994317	2545811	31500045
		1998089	1673447	2491031	2648593	1579009	3759757	1516847	1163993	2130251	1027391	1733873	1852817	2202929	1775219	3946799	31500045
		2547131	2054189	1561247	3773617	2662453	1551289	2217101	1603697	990293	2363453	1538027	712601	4385519	2641649	897779	31500045
		1617347	2434931	2110289	1565149	3745897	2676313	1077143	2043401	1690547	1223237	1342181	2048663	1336499	3508079	3080369	31500045
		1683497	1306373	2616461	682751	976991	872441	1462319	1631771	2759507	2284691	3591143	5556449	1538917	1762177	2774557	31500045
		2801741	1868777	935813	1033751	844061	654371	3248387	1951199	654011	7082519	3810761	539003	3260857	2025217	789577	31500045
		1121093	2431181	2054057	815681	711131	1005371	1142891	2270627	2440079	2065073	4030379	5336831	1275877	2288257	2511517	31500045
		2485421	3196499	4033613	1214971	2270071	2231941	2194883	3140369	4875551	909299	596927	1304111	946823	718379	1381187	31500045
		4786703	3238511	1690319	2922631	1905661	888691	6084269	3403601	722933	1331591	936779	541967	1449827	1015463	581099	31500045
		2443409	3280523	3991601	1579381	1541251	2596351	1931651	3666833	4612319	569447	1276631	964259	649739	1312547	1084103	31500045
		31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045	31500045

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 15. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3.
 See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc				5003331	3	mgc				4811091	3	mgc				7158741
		1597397	1291163	2114771	5003331			1516847	1163993	2130251	4811091			1961537	2714111	2483093	7158741
		2185151	1667777	1150403	5003331			2217101	1603697	990293	4811091			2907803	2386247	1864691	7158741
		1220783	2044391	1738157	5003331			1077143	2043401	1690547	4811091			2289401	2058383	2810957	7158741
		5003331	5003331	5003331	5003331			4811091	4811091	4811091	4811091			7158741	7158741	7158741	7158741
3	mgc				2532183	3	mgc				4703997	3	mgc				2810337
		682751	976991	872441	2532183			1462999	1012831	2228167	4703997			909299	596927	1304111	2810337
		1033751	844061	654371	2532183			2333167	1567999	802831	4703997			1331591	936779	541967	2810337
		815681	711131	1005371	2532183			907831	2123167	1672999	4703997			569447	1276631	964259	2810337
		2532183	2532183	2532183	2532183			4703997	4703997	4703997	4703997			2810337	2810337	2810337	2810337
3	mgc				7206951	3	mgc				5716983	3	mgc				7294317
		1762477	2285683	3158791	7206951			1214971	2270071	2231941	5716983			2317067	1868561	3108689	7294317
		3798631	2402317	1006003	7206951			2922631	1905661	888691	5716983			3223061	2431439	1639817	7294317
		1645843	2518951	3042157	7206951			1579381	1541251	2596351	5716983			1754189	2994317	2545811	7294317
		7206951	7206951	7206951	7206951			5716983	5716983	5716983	5716983			7294317	7294317	7294317	7294317

Example 2. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

15	mgc															15000045
	1779109	370837	850063	1541809	636817	821383	881437	1407409	711163	582949	1892167	524893	1818703	41443	1139863	15000045
	70957	1000003	1929049	279577	1000003	1720429	829729	1000003	1170277	941947	1000003	1058059	321163	1000003	1678843	15000045
	1149943	1629169	220897	1178623	1363189	458197	1288843	592597	1118569	1475113	107839	1417057	860143	1958563	181303	15000045
	547453	1569649	882907	1116889	457117	1426003	1029433	63667	1906909	899917	1439239	660853	1404883	702529	892597	15000045
	1335457	1000003	664549	1309117	1000003	690889	1877479	1000003	122527	760939	1000003	1239067	487717	1000003	1512289	15000045
	1117099	430357	1452553	574003	1542889	883117	93097	1936339	970573	1339153	560767	1100089	1107409	1297477	595123	15000045
	606379	1919677	473953	837139	1999297	163573	1147717	1265119	587173	1406857	734389	858763	740023	1389139	870847	15000045
	867577	1000003	1132429	326437	1000003	1673569	439459	1000003	1560547	451909	1000003	1548097	1130827	1000003	869179	15000045
	1526053	80329	1393627	1836433	709	1162867	1412833	734887	852289	1141243	1265617	593149	1129159	610867	1259983	15000045
	323509	1790707	885793	804157	525979	1669873	600403	1839427	560179	637543	1630927	731539	1123483	1353433	523093	15000045
	1562287	1000003	437719	1865719	1000003	134287	959779	1000003	1040227	1093999	1000003	906007	399613	1000003	1600393	15000045
	1114213	209299	1676497	330133	1474027	1195849	1439827	160579	1399603	1268467	369079	1362463	1476913	646573	876523	15000045
	1055863	131143	1813003	1282543	1009483	707983	343333	1914163	742513	920833	1467589	611587	1254733	994069	751207	15000045
	1757143	1000003	242863	425443	1000003	1574563	1399183	1000003	600823	690757	1000003	1309249	496477	1000003	1503529	15000045
	187003	1868863	944143	1292023	990523	717463	1257493	85843	1656673	1388419	532417	1079173	1248799	1005937	745273	15000045
	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 15. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 3. See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009	3	pan		3000009			
	1779109	370837	850063	3000009		881437	1407409	711163	3000009		1818703	41443	1139863	3000009
	70957	1000003	1929049	3000009		829729	1000003	1170277	3000009		321163	1000003	1678843	3000009
	1149943	1629169	220897	3000009		1288843	592597	1118569	3000009		860143	1958563	181303	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009	3	pan		3000009			
	1116889	457117	1426003	3000009		1147717	1265119	587173	3000009		1406857	734389	858763	3000009
	1309117	1000003	690889	3000009		439459	1000003	1560547	3000009		451909	1000003	1548097	3000009
	574003	1542889	883117	3000009		1412833	734887	852289	3000009		1141243	1265617	593149	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009	3	pan		3000009			
	1055863	131143	1813003	3000009		343333	1914163	742513	3000009		1254733	994069	751207	3000009
	1757143	1000003	242863	3000009		1399183	1000003	600823	3000009		496477	1000003	1503529	3000009
	187003	1868863	944143	3000009		1257493	85843	1656673	3000009		1248799	1005937	745273	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009

Example 3. Different Sums Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

15	mgc														137638695	
	9218123	9237923	9238193	9252863	9236963	8970503	9003803	9004103	9027533	9001523	9277043	9290843	9293363	9296123	9289793	137638695
	9237533	9242483	9223733	9244223	9236093	9002993	9002003	8994053	9008423	8999993	9290123	9294713	9270893	9302693	9288743	137638695
	9238703	9238553	9236813	9235073	9234923	9006953	9007913	9001493	8995073	8996033	9293663	9297413	9289433	9281453	9285203	137638695
	9253043	9229403	9249893	9231143	9220583	9025553	8994563	9008933	9000983	8977433	9297263	9276173	9307973	9284153	9281603	137638695
	9236663	9235703	9235433	9220763	9255503	9001463	8999183	8998883	8975453	9032483	9289073	9288023	9285503	9282743	9301823	137638695
	9208553	9232073	9232673	9239303	9230063	9140093	9178073	9178733	9206663	9176003	9074783	9124133	9126983	9166943	9123623	137638695
	9230183	9229973	9224753	9230873	9226883	9177293	9176813	9163403	9187523	9174533	9124043	9125393	9116033	9128453	9122543	137638695
	9232793	9229433	9228533	9227633	9224273	9190073	9186623	9175913	9165203	9161753	9132323	9126353	9123293	9120233	9114263	137638695
	9244133	9226193	9232313	9227093	9212933	9196283	9164303	9188423	9175013	9155543	9162353	9118133	9130553	9121193	9084233	137638695
	9227003	9224993	9224393	9217763	9248513	9175823	9173753	9173093	9145163	9211733	9122963	9122453	9119603	9079643	9171803	137638695
	9046523	9064193	9064613	9073193	9063443	9319703	9351383	9352253	9377603	9350723	9096203	9118493	9118793	9123833	9117743	137638695
	9063623	9068483	9042353	9076343	9061163	9350813	9356453	9332423	9362123	9349853	9118223	9118853	9104453	9121733	9111803	137638695
	9069503	9070253	9062393	9054533	9055283	9354893	9356003	9350333	9344663	9345773	9119333	9117893	9115013	9112133	9110693	137638695
	9070973	9048443	9082433	9056303	9053813	9376313	9338543	9368243	9344213	9324353	9129023	9108293	9125573	9111173	9101003	137638695
	9061343	9060593	9060173	9051593	9078263	9349943	9349283	9348413	9323063	9380963	9112283	9111533	9111233	9106193	9133823	137638695
	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695	137638695

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 15. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 5.

See below few examples of order 5:

5	mgc						46184065	5	mgc						45007465
		9218123	9237923	9238193	9252863	9236963	46184065			8970503	9003803	9004103	9027533	9001523	45007465
		9237533	9242483	9223733	9244223	9236093	46184065			9002993	9002003	8994053	9008423	8999993	45007465
		9238703	9238553	9236813	9235073	9234923	46184065			9006953	9007913	9001493	8995073	8996033	45007465
		9253043	9229403	9249893	9231143	9220583	46184065			9025553	8994563	9008933	9000983	8977433	45007465
		9236663	9235703	9235433	9220763	9255503	46184065			9001463	8999183	8998883	8975453	9032483	45007465
		46184065	46184065	46184065	46184065	46184065	46184065			45007465	45007465	45007465	45007465	45007465	45007465
5	mgc						46142665	5	mgc						45879565
		9208553	9232073	9232673	9239303	9230063	46142665			9140093	9178073	9178733	9206663	9176003	45879565
		9230183	9229973	9224753	9230873	9226883	46142665			9177293	9176813	9163403	9187523	9174533	45879565
		9232793	9229433	9228533	9227633	9224273	46142665			9190073	9186623	9175913	9165203	9161753	45879565
		9244133	9226193	9232313	9227093	9212933	46142665			9196283	9164303	9188423	9175013	9155543	45879565
		9227003	9224993	9224393	9217763	9248513	46142665			9175823	9173753	9173093	9145163	9211733	45879565
		46142665	46142665	46142665	46142665	46142665	46142665			45879565	45879565	45879565	45879565	45879565	45879565
5	mgc						45311965	5	mgc						46751665
		9046523	9064193	9064613	9073193	9063443	45311965			9319703	9351383	9352253	9377603	9350723	46751665
		9063623	9068483	9042353	9076343	9061163	45311965			9350813	9356453	9332423	9362123	9349853	46751665
		9069503	9070253	9062393	9054533	9055283	45311965			9354893	9356003	9350333	9344663	9345773	46751665
		9070973	9048443	9082433	9056303	9053813	45311965			9376313	9338543	9368243	9344213	9324353	46751665
		9061343	9060593	9060173	9051593	9078263	45311965			9349943	9349283	9348413	9323063	9380963	46751665
		45311965	45311965	45311965	45311965	45311965	45311965			46751665	46751665	46751665	46751665	46751665	46751665

Example 4. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

15	mgc															15000045
	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	15000045
	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	15000045
	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	15000045
	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	15000045
	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	15000045
	1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	15000045
	1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	15000045
	566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	15000045
	1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	15000045
	214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	15000045
	1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	15000045
	851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	15000045
	1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	15000045
	789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	15000045
	18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	15000045
	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 15. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 5. See below few examples of order 5:

3	mgc				3000009		3	mgc				3000009		3	mgc				3000009				
	1004287	305029	1690693	3000009			1164607	876229	959173	3000009			1488793	721387	789829	3000009			3000009				
	1686409	1000003	313597	3000009			794569	1000003	1205437	3000009			301039	1000003	1698967	3000009			3000009				
	309313	1694977	995719	3000009			1040833	1123777	835399	3000009			1210177	1278619	511213	3000009			3000009				
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009			3000009				
5	mgc					5000015		5	mgc					5000015		5	mgc					5000015	
	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	5000015			829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	5000015			1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	5000015	
	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	5000015			1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	5000015			969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	5000015	
	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	5000015			1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	5000015			1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	5000015	
	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	5000015			1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	5000015			600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	5000015	
	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	5000015			7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	5000015			350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	5000015	
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015			5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015			5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015

Example 5. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

15	mgc															15000045
	518863	765319	665773	815257	1490557	1299877	1264699	1183969	435763	1547419	518509	1395187	874813	621337	1602703	15000045
	1230967	1281349	617917	329473	1633729	434347	509359	1173343	1476799	1654369	1321429	1402603	589273	576049	769039	15000045
	922549	1404427	895393	1297393	767293	1241077	735979	1179733	1370227	965023	963793	499183	1084939	595579	1077457	15000045
	1120807	541837	441697	1866967	1443157	1140913	1417057	702607	963643	1024579	302857	138247	1558309	1458169	879199	15000045
	1230343	788353	1087657	719833	464419	740023	824497	1622743	370423	1404163	1573753	1280173	912349	1211653	769663	15000045
	1327063	1087027	550177	410323	1648789	405667	1321357	518767	1368187	1386037	351217	1589683	1449829	912979	672943	15000045
	661663	1020037	1081813	570637	1446457	1256737	758743	736927	1504339	743269	553549	1429369	918193	979969	1338343	15000045
	441619	1518067	578923	312349	1280857	1578019	1745599	1000003	254407	421987	719149	1687657	1421083	481939	1558387	15000045
	1533439	730999	1386013	1182403	1541143	1145623	495667	1263079	1241263	854383	458863	817603	613993	1269007	466567	15000045
	968299	329083	1669873	308527	192103	613969	678649	1481239	631819	1594339	1807903	1691479	330133	1670923	1031707	15000045
	1371949	1393159	1416097	1767229	426253	1259983	1175509	377263	1629583	595843	1535587	232777	583909	606847	628057	15000045
	862669	487447	977323	1861759	556849	859093	582949	1297399	1036363	975427	1697149	133039	1022683	1512559	1137337	15000045
	752449	994297	915067	702613	1232713	758929	1264027	820273	629779	1034983	1036213	1500823	1104613	1005709	1247557	15000045
	1660063	1423957	1382089	1670533	366277	1565659	1490647	826663	523207	345637	678577	597403	1410733	718657	339943	15000045
	397303	1234687	1334233	1184749	509449	700129	735307	816037	1564243	452587	1481497	604819	1125193	1378669	1481143	15000045
	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045	15000045

It is block-bordered prime magic square of order 15. It is composed of equal sums cocentric prime magic squares of order 5. It contains prime magic squares of order 3. See below few examples of orders 5 and 3:

11	mgc											11000033						
	895393	1297393	767293	1241077	735979	1179733	1370227	965023	963793	499183	1084939	11000033						
	441697	1866967	1443157	1140913	1417057	702607	963643	1024579	302857	138247	1558309	11000033						
	1087657	719833	464419	740023	824497	1622743	370423	1404163	1573753	1280173	912349	11000033						
	550177	410323	1648789	405667	1321357	518767	1368187	1386037	351217	1589683	1449829	11000033						
	1081813	570637	1446457	1256737	758743	736927	1504339	743269	553549	1429369	918193	11000033						
	578923	312349	1280857	1578019	1745599	1000003	254407	421987	719149	1687657	1421083	11000033						
	1386013	1182403	1541143	1145623	495667	1263079	1241263	854383	458863	817603	613993	11000033						
	1669873	308527	192103	613969	678649	1481239	631819	1594339	1807903	1691479	330133	11000033						
	1416097	1767229	426253	1259983	1175509	377263	1629583	595843	1535587	232777	583909	11000033						
	977323	1861759	556849	859093	582949	1297399	1036363	975427	1697149	133039	1022683	11000033						
	915067	702613	1232713	758929	1264027	820273	629779	1034983	1036213	1500823	1104613	11000033						
	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033	11000033						
3	mgc							3000009										
	758743	736927	1504339					3000009										
	1745599	1000003	254407					3000009										
	495667	1263079	1241263					3000009										
	3000009	3000009	3000009					3000009										
5	mgc										5000015							
	405667	1321357	518767	1368187	1386037						5000015							
	1256737	758743	736927	1504339	743269						5000015							
	1578019	1745599	1000003	254407	421987						5000015							
	1145623	495667	1263079	1241263	854383						5000015							
	613969	678649	1481239	631819	1594339						5000015							
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015						5000015							
7	mgc												7000021					
	464419	740023	824497	1622743	370423	1404163	1573753							7000021				
	1648789	405667	1321357	518767	1368187	1386037	351217							7000021				
	1446457	1256737	758743	736927	1504339	743269	553549							7000021				
	1280857	1578019	1745599	1000003	254407	421987	719149							7000021				
	1541143	1145623	495667	1263079	1241263	854383	458863							7000021				
	192103	613969	678649	1481239	631819	1594339	1807903							7000021				
	426253	1259983	1175509	377263	1629583	595843	1535587							7000021				
	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021	7000021							7000021				
9	mgc																9000027	
	1866967	1443157	1140913	1417057	702607	963643	1024579	302857	138247									9000027
	719833	464419	740023	824497	1622743	370423	1404163	1573753	1280173									9000027
	410323	1648789	405667	1321357	518767	1368187	1386037	351217	1589683									9000027
	570637	1446457	1256737	758743	736927	1504339	743269	553549	1429369									9000027
	312349	1280857	1578019	1745599	1000003	254407	421987	719149	1687657									9000027
	1182403	1541143	1145623	495667	1263079	1241263	854383	458863	817603									9000027
	308527	192103	613969	678649	1481239	631819	1594339	1807903	1691479									9000027
	1767229	426253	1259983	1175509	377263	1629583	595843	1535587	232777									9000027
	1861759	556849	859093	582949	1297399	1036363	975427	1697149	133039									9000027
	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027	9000027									9000027
13	mgc												13000039					
	1281349	617917	329473	1633729	434347	509359	1173343	1476799	1654369	1321429	1402603	589273	576049	13000039				
	1404427	895393	1297393	767293	1241077	735979	1179733	1370227	965023	963793	499183	1084939	595579	13000039				
	541837	441697	1866967	1443157	1140913	1417057	702607	963643	1024579	302857	138247	1558309	1458169	13000039				
	788353	1087657	719833	464419	740023	824497	1622743	370423	1404163	1573753	1280173	912349	1211653	13000039				
	1087027	550177	410323	1648789	405667	1321357	518767	1368187	1386037	351217	1589683	1449829	912979	13000039				
	1020037	1081813	570637	1446457	1256737	758743	736927	1504339	743269	553549	1429369	918193	979969	13000039				
	1518067	578923	312349	1280857	1578019	1745599	1000003	254407	421987	719149	1687657	1421083	481939	13000039				
	730999	1386013	1182403	1541143	1145623	495667	1263079	1241263	854383	458863	817603	613993	1269007	13000039				
	329083	1669873	308527	192103	613969	678649	1481239	631819	1594339	1807903	1691479	330133	1670923	13000039				
	1393159	1416097	1767229	426253	1259983	1175509	377263	1629583	595843	1535587	232777	583909	606847	13000039				
	487447	977323	1861759	556849	859093	582949	1297399	1036363	975427	1697149	133039	1022683	1512559	13000039				
	994297	915067	702613	1232713	758929	1264027	820273	629779	1034983	1036213	1500823	1104613	1005709	13000039				
	1423957	1382089	1670533	366277	1565659	1490647	826663	523207	345637	678577	597403	1410733	718657	13000039				
	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039	13000039				

3.2 Prime Magic Squares of Order 16

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 16 with different representations.

Example 6. Different Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

16	mgc																32000000
	2497751	1921267	1876187	1476359	1881521	2259703	1563743	2488469	1294351	1481167	2379761	2039509	2266247	1641593	2603849	2328523	32000000
	2314199	2326517	1634267	1496581	2574521	1876367	2253497	1489051	1772167	2047061	1774027	1601533	1943653	2257103	2475989	2163467	32000000
	1470407	3171731	639049	2490377	2420867	2134943	1928629	1708997	2308261	1561243	1812457	1512827	2349251	1754639	2352481	2383841	32000000
	1489207	352049	3622061	2308247	1316527	1922423	2447567	2506919	1820009	2105317	1228543	2040919	2281061	3186877	1407893	1964381	32000000
	2542649	2110133	2341463	1555951	1983479	1785331	2750773	2493301	2182529	1786501	1858163	2609219	1640273	1264199	1116893	1979143	32000000
	2010167	2248663	2458019	1833347	2544907	2132359	2520241	1815377	2064431	2163431	1680319	2528231	996599	1866037	1253279	1884593	32000000
	2111731	2650577	1192937	2594951	2429437	1944281	2416003	2223163	2702509	2659931	1932731	1141241	1599583	1004033	1877159	1519733	32000000
	1885649	1540823	2557777	2565947	2055061	3150913	1325867	2481043	1486943	1826549	2965199	2157721	1764053	1866239	1753177	617039	32000000
	1370389	2048939	1452863	1037261	1535587	1317299	1414319	687383	2004833	2668637	2563147	2359499	3457897	2391847	3330949	2359151	32000000
	1670831	1371581	1716311	1150729	1258181	1197467	1597943	900997	2101423	2559773	2768897	2166023	3252061	3303623	2441161	2542999	32000000
	1950941	2238589	582971	1136951	1585589	2094031	65147	1209821	2152817	1130677	3136769	3175853	2745497	4655143	1139917	2999287	32000000
	917291	250343	2157307	2584511	575231	345791	1877179	2156387	3337043	3237029	1127303	1894741	2084389	1189231	4627817	3638407	32000000
	2444111	2346347	3013847	1964483	2471449	2384339	2979173	2004131	1656841	2122363	1477291	1516189	1300841	1335287	1926937	1056371	32000000
	2356463	2869883	2624711	1917731	2610317	2551733	2518903	2158139	1147969	1803163	2081311	1740241	1666447	903899	1700129	1348961	32000000
	2792717	3004097	1270097	2701877	2104217	2662949	2105507	2966419	1149901	357211	2530999	2734573	863771	1074559	1940849	1740257	32000000
	2175497	1548461	2860133	3184697	2653109	2240071	2235509	2710403	2817973	2489947	683083	781681	1788377	2305691	51521	1473847	32000000
	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000	32000000

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 16. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 4.
 See below few examples of order 4:

4	mgc					7771564	4	mgc					8193436
	2497751	1921267	1876187	1476359	7771564		1881521	2259703	1563743	2488469	8193436		
	2314199	2326517	1634267	1496581	7771564		2574521	1876367	2253497	1489051	8193436		
	1470407	3171731	639049	2490377	7771564		2420867	2134943	1928629	1708997	8193436		
	1489207	352049	3622061	2308247	7771564		1316527	1922423	2447567	2506919	8193436		
	7771564	7771564	7771564	7771564	7771564		8193436	8193436	8193436	8193436	8193436		
4	mgc					8550196	4	mgc					9012884
	2542649	2110133	2341463	1555951	8550196		1983479	1785331	2750773	2493301	9012884		
	2010167	2248663	2458019	1833347	8550196		2544907	2132359	2520241	1815377	9012884		
	2111731	2650577	1192937	2594951	8550196		2429437	1944281	2416003	2223163	9012884		
	1885649	1540823	2557777	2565947	8550196		2055061	3150913	1325867	2481043	9012884		
	8550196	8550196	8550196	8550196	8550196		9012884	9012884	9012884	9012884	9012884		
4	mgc					5909452	4	mgc					4954588
	1370389	2048939	1452863	1037261	5909452		1535587	1317299	1414319	687383	4954588		
	1670831	1371581	1716311	1150729	5909452		1258181	1197467	1597943	900997	4954588		
	1950941	2238589	582971	1136951	5909452		1585589	2094031	65147	1209821	4954588		
	917291	250343	2157307	2584511	5909452		575231	345791	1877179	2156387	4954588		
	5909452	5909452	5909452	5909452	5909452		4954588	4954588	4954588	4954588	4954588		

Example 7. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

16	mgc																16000048
	1448989	621337	1378669	551017	1101253	889879	1110127	898753	1164967	918193	1081813	835039	1172467	922333	1077673	827539	16000048
	603817	1823149	176857	1396189	907723	1746127	253879	1092283	849019	1682413	317593	1150987	862669	1674913	325093	1137337	16000048
	129127	1454059	545947	1870879	281539	1137883	862123	1718467	308359	1169713	830293	1691647	291349	1173853	826153	1708657	16000048
	1818079	101467	1898539	181927	1709497	226123	1773883	290509	1677667	229693	1770313	322339	1673527	228913	1771093	326479	16000048
	1752397	251359	1748647	247609	1781173	258109	1741897	218833	1638913	329347	1670659	361093	1678639	354877	1645129	321367	16000048
	307423	1877353	122653	1692583	283303	1848577	151429	1716703	401053	1903339	96667	1598953	331777	1863613	136393	1668229	16000048
	80629	1770187	229819	1919377	90403	1784617	215389	1909603	94327	1676533	323473	1905679	126037	1678693	321313	1873969	16000048
	1859563	101113	1898893	140443	1845133	108709	1891297	154873	1865719	90793	1909213	134287	1863559	102829	1897177	136447	16000048
	1782289	235273	1764733	217717	1788433	209857	1790149	211573	1325557	661099	1338907	674449	1364617	666889	1333117	635389	16000048
	258127	1866973	133033	1741879	243829	1860829	139177	1756177	692239	1873507	126499	1307767	648259	1834447	165559	1351747	16000048
	93553	1783219	216787	1906453	108517	1790029	209977	1891489	122209	1339057	660949	1877797	155689	1367617	632389	1844317	16000048
	1866043	114547	1885459	133963	1859233	139297	1860709	140773	1860007	126349	1873657	139999	1831447	131059	1868947	168559	16000048
	1175569	836863	1163143	824437	1200349	861823	1138183	799657	1219843	857407	1142599	780163	1674997	288913	1711093	325009	16000048
	867487	1805653	194353	1132519	878833	1780873	219133	1121173	868957	1761379	238627	1131049	295129	1887433	112573	1704877	16000048
	163573	1187839	812167	1836433	150247	1210639	789367	1849759	176629	1246639	753367	1823377	181219	1713763	286243	1818787	16000048
	1793383	169657	1830349	206623	1770583	146677	1853329	229423	1734583	134587	1865419	265423	1848667	109903	1890103	151339	16000048
	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 16. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 6. See below few examples of order 6:

4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
		1448989	621337	1378669	551017	4000012			1638913	329347	1670659	361093	4000012
		603817	1823149	176857	1396189	4000012			401053	1903339	96667	1598953	4000012
		129127	1454059	545947	1870879	4000012			94327	1676533	323473	1905679	4000012
		1818079	101467	1898539	181927	4000012			1865719	90793	1909213	134287	4000012
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012			4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012
4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
		1781173	258109	1741897	218833	4000012			1219843	857407	1142599	780163	4000012
		283303	1848577	151429	1716703	4000012			868957	1761379	238627	1131049	4000012
		90403	1784617	215389	1909603	4000012			176629	1246639	753367	1823377	4000012
		1845133	108709	1891297	154873	4000012			1734583	134587	1865419	265423	4000012
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012			4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012
4	mgc					4000012	4	mgc					4000012
		1788433	209857	1790149	211573	4000012			1678639	354877	1645129	321367	4000012
		243829	1860829	139177	1756177	4000012			331777	1863613	136393	1668229	4000012
		108517	1790029	209977	1891489	4000012			126037	1678693	321313	1873969	4000012
		1859233	139297	1860709	140773	4000012			1863559	102829	1897177	136447	4000012
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012			4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012

Example 8. Different Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

16	mgc															16000048		
		628819	1175467	932647	1143949	1249849	918067	564097	1387129	1941799	1642447	1655323	1022377	327889	521119	512467	376603	16000048
		355063	1335637	1591237	1480483	620623	332779	639259	1644943	929749	1892887	424423	783019	1486699	1288423	124567	1070257	16000048
		1265863	842077	980179	582727	1417279	1019827	1157929	734143	720547	600217	1034983	1108729	891277	965023	1399789	1279459	16000048
		1537399	882907	948187	1362763	637243	1051819	1117099	462607	473953	431833	1338109	1139917	860089	661897	1568173	1526053	16000048
		889027	1297693	753367	1024663	975343	1246639	702313	1110979	1152793	465679	1176433	1724413	275593	823573	1534327	847213	16000048
		1085767	280957	1318279	1029859	970147	681727	1719049	914239	397303	733963	450487	26953	1973053	1549519	1266043	1602703	16000048
		1625209	1360747	408769	519523	1379383	1667227	664369	374797	760477	1875439	1575583	1216987	513307	711583	107119	1239529	16000048
		612877	824539	1067359	856057	750157	1081939	1435909	1371187	1623403	357559	344683	977629	1672117	1478887	1487539	58207	16000048
		1975243	367867	1511863	670693	1404289	1075237	988789	6043	166987	1143697	423463	1548307	802969	1372207	724447	1817947	16000048
		605617	1646209	402307	1255693	1227337	1280113	188359	1394389	1147969	1325557	1078849	577639	1101193	1065763	851017	852037	16000048
		631753	1280863	1081219	927643	1072363	918787	719143	1368253	1351747	318979	1416769	1288033	711973	583237	1681027	648259	16000048
		527749	589063	1123807	729577	1270429	876199	1410943	1472257	1022899	1210897	642253	745993	1254013	1357753	789109	977107	16000048
		538303	626947	1263943	1279753	720253	736063	1373059	1461703	1687657	783613	1340947	1562719	437287	659059	1216393	312349	16000048
		1424803	45289	531043	1063039	936967	1468963	1954717	575203	485593	1211983	600043	403267	1596739	1399963	788023	1514413	16000048
		302593	1811647	1597699	744313	772669	719893	353797	1697413	1955113	1148989	921157	1422367	898813	934243	674449	44893	16000048
		1993963	1632139	488143	1329313	595717	924769	1011217	24763	182059	856309	1576543	451699	1197037	627799	1275559	1833019	16000048
		16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048	16000048

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 16. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 8.

See below few examples of order 8:

4	mgc					4000012														
		980179	582727	1417279	1019827	4000012														
		948187	1362763	637243	1051819	4000012														
		753367	1024663	975343	1246639	4000012														
		1318279	1029859	970147	681727	4000012														
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012														
4	mgc					4000012														
		1034983	1108729	891277	965023	4000012														
		1338109	1139917	860089	661897	4000012														
		1176433	1724413	275593	823573	4000012														
		450487	26953	1973053	1549519	4000012														
		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012														
6	mgc						6000018													
		1335637	1591237	1480483	620623	332779	639259	6000018												
		842077	980179	582727	1417279	1019827	1157929	6000018												
		882907	948187	1362763	637243	1051819	1117099	6000018												
		1297693	753367	1024663	975343	1246639	702313	6000018												
		280957	1318279	1029859	970147	681727	1719049	6000018												
		1360747	408769	519523	1379383	1667227	664369	6000018												
		6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018												
6	mgc						6000018													
		1892887	424423	783019	1486699	1288423	124567	6000018												
		600217	1034983	1108729	891277	965023	1399789	6000018												
		431833	1338109	1139917	860089	661897	1568173	6000018												
		465679	1176433	1724413	275593	823573	1534327	6000018												
		733963	450487	26953	1973053	1549519	1266043	6000018												
		1875439	1575583	1216987	513307	711583	107119	6000018												
		6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018												
8	mgc								8000024											
		628819	1175467	932647	1143949	1249849	918067	564097	1387129	8000024										
		355063	1335637	1591237	1480483	620623	332779	639259	1644943	8000024										
		1265863	842077	980179	582727	1417279	1019827	1157929	734143	8000024										
		1537399	882907	948187	1362763	637243	1051819	1117099	462607	8000024										
		889027	1297693	753367	1024663	975343	1246639	702313	1110979	8000024										
		1085767	280957	1318279	1029859	970147	681727	1719049	914239	8000024										
		1625209	1360747	408769	519523	1379383	1667227	664369	374797	8000024										
		612877	824539	1067359	856057	750157	1081939	1435909	1371187	8000024										
		8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024										
8	mgc								8000024											
		1941799	1642447	1655323	1022377	327889	521119	512467	376603	8000024										
		929749	1892887	424423	783019	1486699	1288423	124567	1070257	8000024										
		720547	600217	1034983	1108729	891277	965023	1399789	1279459	8000024										
		473953	431833	1338109	1139917	860089	661897	1568173	1526053	8000024										
		1152793	465679	1176433	1724413	275593	823573	1534327	847213	8000024										
		397303	733963	450487	26953	1973053	1549519	1266043	1602703	8000024										
		760477	1875439	1575583	1216987	513307	711583	107119	1239529	8000024										
		1623403	357559	344683	977629	1672117	1478887	1487539	58207	8000024										
		8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024	8000024										

Example 9. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

16	mgc															8000000	
	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	8000000
	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	8000000
	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	8000000
	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	8000000
	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	8000000
	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	8000000
	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	8000000
	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	8000000
	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	8000000
	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	8000000
	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	8000000
	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	8000000
	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	8000000
	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	8000000
	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	8000000
	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	8000000
	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000	8000000

It is **single-layer-bordered prime magic square** of order 16. The internal block of order 14 is also a concentric single-layer bordered magic square of order 14 studied in previous part.

3.3 Prime Magic Squares of Order 17

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 17 with different representations.

Example 10. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

17	mgc															35700051		
	3071897	2840657	937577	1604573	79103	3103579	2954417	861493	2439893	2131417	3576323	2108737	1634603	3961057	1956529	1293917	1144279	35700051
	1964063	1597397	1291163	2114771	1754497	2407549	3894523	1075241	2140847	2704469	1113221	1616597	2631029	1961537	2714111	2483093	2235943	35700051
	715223	2185151	1667777	1150403	4825549	2685523	545497	3602747	1973519	344291	3304757	1786949	269141	2907803	2386247	1864691	3484783	35700051
	3813463	1220783	2044391	1738157	1476523	2963497	3616549	1242569	1806191	2871797	942869	1957301	2460677	2289401	2058383	2810957	386543	35700051
	3263627	1666081	1143049	2203153	1762477	2285683	3158791	1462999	1012831	2228167	1709671	2380387	3192439	2317067	1868561	3108689	936379	35700051
	1295113	2207833	1670761	1133689	3798631	2402317	1006003	2333167	1567999	802831	3910267	2427499	944731	3223061	2431439	1639817	2904893	35700051
	3087457	1138369	2198473	1675441	1645843	2518951	3042157	907831	2123167	1672999	1662559	2474611	3145327	1754189	2994317	2545811	1112549	35700051
	133439	1998089	1673447	2491031	2648593	1579009	3759757	1516847	1163993	2130251	1027391	1733873	1852817	2202929	1775219	3946799	4066567	35700051
	1352167	2547131	2054189	1561247	3773617	2662453	1551289	2217101	1603697	990293	2363453	1538027	712601	4385519	2641649	897779	2847839	35700051
	3206303	1617347	2434931	2110289	1565149	3745897	2676313	1077143	2043401	1690547	1223237	1342181	2048663	1336499	3508079	3080369	993703	35700051
	1710529	1683497	1306373	2616461	682751	976991	872441	1462319	1631771	2759507	2284691	3591143	5556449	1538917	1762177	2774557	2489477	35700051
	2399477	2801741	1868777	935813	1033751	844061	654371	3248387	1951199	654011	7082519	3810761	539003	3260857	2025217	789577	1800529	35700051
	392467	1121093	2431181	2054057	815681	711131	1005371	1142891	2270627	2440079	2065073	4030379	5336831	1275877	2288257	2511517	3807539	35700051
	1840057	2485421	3196499	4033613	1214971	2270071	2231941	2194883	3140369	4875551	909299	596927	1304111	946823	718379	1381187	2359949	35700051
	739649	4786703	3238511	1690319	2922631	1905661	888691	6084269	3403601	722933	1331591	936779	541967	1449827	1015463	581099	3460357	35700051
	3659393	2443409	3280523	3991601	1579381	1541251	2596351	1931651	3666833	4612319	569447	1276631	964259	649739	1312547	1084103	540613	35700051
	3055727	1359349	3262429	2595433	4120903	1096427	1245589	3338513	1760113	2068589	623683	2091269	2565403	238949	2243477	2906089	1128109	35700051
	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051	35700051

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 17 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.1.

Example 11. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

17	mgc																17000051	
	1176433	603769	1917397	1998343	99817	1345453	102367	1720189	834859	1474069	1491643	628057	442579	170389	1084459	818359	1091869	17000051
	1310137	1779109	370837	850063	1541809	636817	821383	881437	1407409	711163	582949	1892167	524893	1818703	41443	1139863	689869	17000051
	1402603	70957	1000003	1929049	279577	1000003	1720429	829729	1000003	1170277	941947	1000003	1058059	321163	1000003	1678843	597403	17000051
	1389559	1149943	1629169	220897	1178623	1363189	458197	1288843	592597	1118569	1475113	107839	1417057	860143	1958563	181303	610447	17000051
	1025047	547453	1569649	882907	1116889	457117	1426003	1029433	63667	1906909	899917	1439239	660853	1404883	702529	892597	974959	17000051
	1369483	1335457	1000003	664549	1309117	1000003	690889	1877479	1000003	122527	760939	1000003	1239067	487717	1000003	1512289	630523	17000051
	543883	1117099	430357	1452553	574003	1542889	883117	93097	1936339	970573	1339153	560767	1100089	1107409	1297477	595123	1456123	17000051
	186679	606379	1919677	473953	837139	1999297	163573	1147717	1265119	587173	1406857	734389	858763	740023	1389139	870847	1813327	17000051
	1135903	867577	1000003	1132429	326437	1000003	1673569	439459	1000003	1560547	451909	1000003	1548097	1130827	1000003	869179	864103	17000051
	1026547	1526053	80329	1393627	1836433	709	1162867	1412833	734887	852289	1141243	1265617	593149	1129159	610867	1259983	973459	17000051
	326149	323509	1790707	885793	804157	525979	1669873	600403	1839427	560179	637543	1630927	731539	1123483	1353433	523093	1673857	17000051
	1874143	1562287	1000003	437719	1865719	1000003	134287	959779	1000003	1040227	1093999	1000003	906007	399613	1000003	1600393	125863	17000051
	783829	1114213	209299	1676497	330133	1474027	1195849	1439827	160579	1399603	1268467	369079	1362463	1476913	646573	876523	1216177	17000051
	792307	1055863	131143	1813003	1282543	1009483	707983	343333	1914163	742513	920833	1467589	611587	1254733	994069	751207	1207699	17000051
	1382023	1757143	1000003	242863	425443	1000003	1574563	1399183	1000003	600823	690757	1000003	1309249	496477	1000003	1503529	617983	17000051
	367189	187003	1868863	944143	1292023	990523	717463	1257493	85843	1656673	1388419	532417	1079173	1248799	1005937	745273	1632817	17000051
	908137	1396237	82609	1663	1900189	654553	1897639	279817	1165147	525937	508363	1371949	1557427	1829617	915547	1181647	823573	17000051
	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 17 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 3. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.2.

Example 12. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Cocentric Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

17	mgc																155990521	
	4579637	17017457	10557359	11742989	8459813	4395869	328277	2110217	17895089	2432093	2204507	9744797	15177089	4624787	16038839	15372779	13308923	155990521
	17628263	9218123	9237923	9238193	9252863	9236963	8970503	9003803	9004103	9027533	9001523	9277043	9290843	9293363	9296123	9289793	723563	155990521
	15976589	9237533	9242483	9223733	9244223	9236093	9002993	9002003	8994053	9008423	8999993	9290123	9294713	9270893	9302693	9288743	2375237	155990521
	7424909	9238703	9238553	9236813	9235073	9234923	9006953	9007913	9001493	8995073	8996033	9293663	9297413	9289433	9281453	9285203	10926917	155990521
	6852917	9253043	9229403	9249893	9231143	9220583	9025553	8994563	9008933	9000983	8977433	9297263	9276173	9307973	9284153	9281603	11498909	155990521
	5636789	9236663	9235703	9235433	9220763	9255503	9001463	8999183	8998883	8975453	9032483	9289073	9288023	9285503	9282743	9301823	12715037	155990521
	6271127	9208553	9232073	9232673	9239303	9230063	9140093	9178073	9178733	9206663	9176003	9074783	9124133	9126983	9166943	9123623	12080699	155990521
	18328547	9230183	9229973	9224753	9230873	9226883	9177293	9176813	9163403	9187523	9174533	9124043	9125393	9116033	9128453	9122543	23279	155990521
	9831863	9232793	9229433	9228533	9227633	9224273	9190073	9186623	9175913	9165203	9161753	9132323	9126353	9123293	9120233	9114263	8519963	155990521
	3836867	9244133	9226193	9232313	9227093	9212933	9196283	9164303	9188423	9175013	9155543	9162353	9118133	9130553	9121193	9084233	14514959	155990521
	9023327	9227003	9224993	9224393	9217763	9248513	9175823	9173753	9173093	9145163	9211733	9122963	9122453	9119603	9079643	9171803	9328499	155990521
	3930257	9046523	9064193	9064613	9073193	9063443	9319703	9351383	9352253	9377603	9350723	9096203	9118493	9118793	9123833	9117743	14421569	155990521
	15213923	9063623	9068483	9042353	9076343	9061163	9350813	9356453	9332423	9362123	9349853	9118223	9118853	9104453	9121733	9111803	3137903	155990521
	7408007	9069503	9070253	9062393	9054533	9055283	9354893	9356003	9350333	9344663	9345773	9119333	9117893	9115013	9112133	9110693	10943819	155990521
	15467939	9070973	9048443	9082433	9056303	9053813	9376313	9338543	9368243	9344213	9324353	9129023	9108293	9125573	9111173	9101003	2883887	155990521
	3536657	9061343	9060593	9060173	9051593	9078263	9349943	9349283	9348413	9323063	9380963	9112283	9111533	9111233	9106193	9133823	14815169	155990521
	5042903	1334369	7794467	6608837	9892013	13955957	18023549	16241609	456737	15919733	16147319	8607029	3174737	13727039	2312987	2979047	13772189	155990521
	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521	155990521

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 17 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **different sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 5. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.3.

Example 13. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Concentric Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

17	mgc																17000051	
	316957	1056793	121309	1211059	1799599	310729	1038259	500839	809983	662107	1267009	1990327	1254637	1936609	88903	686143	1948789	17000051
	901339	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	1098667	17000051
	1974787	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	25219	17000051
	1710517	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	289489	17000051
	272179	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	1727827	17000051
	152443	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	1847563	17000051
	643507	1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	1356499	17000051
	1721449	1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	278557	17000051
	1049479	566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	950527	17000051
	1569703	1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	430303	17000051
	1457059	214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	542947	17000051
	1003819	1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	996187	17000051
	1370977	851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	629029	17000051
	230467	1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	1769539	17000051
	1704103	789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	295903	17000051
	870049	18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	1129957	17000051
	51217	943213	1878697	788947	200407	1689277	961747	1499167	1190023	1337899	732997	9679	745369	63397	1911103	1313863	1683049	17000051
	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 17 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **equal sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 5. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.4.

Example 14. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

17	mgc																17000051	
	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	17000051
	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	17000051
	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	17000051
	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	17000051
	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	17000051
	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	17000051
	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	17000051
	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	17000051
	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	17000051
	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	17000051
	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	17000051
	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	17000051
	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	17000051
	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	17000051
	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	17000051
	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	17000051
	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	17000051
	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051	17000051

It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 17. The internal layer are also prime magic squares of orders 15, 13, 11, 9, 7, 5 and 3. It is the same as given in Example 3.5.

3.4 Prime Magic Squares of Order 18

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 18 with different representations.

Example 15. Different Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

18	mgc																	36000000	
	1359937	1942207	2317927	995227	1901131	2505499	1951739	2041967	2068673	1664863	2803819	2378737	1482431	2532161	2634461	1468967	2115653	1834601	36000000
	2831347	1873357	915367	3310891	1800619	290347	2137727	2020793	1903859	2996347	2282473	1568599	3368381	2216351	1064321	2172041	1806407	1440773	36000000
	1428787	1804507	2386777	1095739	1700107	2606011	1972913	1999619	2089847	2186209	1761127	2900083	1798241	1900541	2950271	1778213	1497161	2143847	36000000
	1258097	2881031	2247053	1460653	2238277	3188089	1874987	1270421	2599613	1180519	2434387	2020771	1060453	2014069	2308561	1373027	1613069	2976923	36000000
	3117683	2128727	1139771	4023109	2295673	568237	2639633	1915007	1190381	2718811	1878559	1038307	3042469	1794361	546253	3591569	1987673	383777	36000000
	2010401	1376423	2999357	1403257	2353069	3130693	1230401	2559593	1955027	1736347	1322731	2576599	1280161	1574653	2528269	998423	2362277	2602319	36000000
	958007	1850831	2597513	1335619	1926667	2258083	1338517	2442673	2224171	1363403	2596667	2527919	2119261	1833523	2893987	1644653	1319429	2769077	36000000
	3441623	1802117	162611	2762587	1840123	917659	2887441	2001787	1116133	3327179	2162663	998147	3056983	2282257	1507531	3035477	1911053	786629	36000000
	1006721	1753403	2646227	1422163	1753579	2344627	1779403	1560901	2665057	1797407	1728659	2961923	1670527	2730991	2445253	1053029	2502677	2177453	36000000
	2120941	1738117	2565649	1042141	2655643	1888897	1662611	2028773	2893967	1687247	2052371	2025923	1284007	1430593	2412541	1523813	1801673	3185093	36000000
	2586277	2141569	1696861	2708983	1862227	1015471	3426473	2195117	963761	2260523	1921847	1583171	2837581	1709047	580513	3831473	2170193	508913	36000000
	1717489	2545021	2162197	1835557	1068811	2682313	1496267	2361461	2727623	1817771	1791323	2156447	1005553	1987501	2134087	1155293	2538713	2816573	36000000
	3067367	2197733	5103221	3439309	3436291	3454387	2138743	3279517	4511029	335857	544543	712531	322073	625367	616289	646883	727169	841691	36000000
	5491961	3456107	1420253	3458407	3443329	3428251	5682049	3309763	937477	907651	530977	154303	815459	521243	227027	933389	738581	543773	36000000
	1808993	4714481	3844847	3432271	3450367	3447349	2108497	3340009	4480783	349423	517411	726097	426197	417119	720413	635471	749993	830279	36000000
	541693	402847	849829	436279	853999	983809	368833	586849	716917	1936871	3567989	4165583	2907899	2389733	5132591	3191423	3427469	3539387	36000000
	906259	598123	289987	1305559	758029	210499	905617	557533	209449	5452193	3223481	994769	5701433	3476741	1252049	3734057	3386093	3038129	36000000
	346417	793399	654553	532249	662059	1079779	398149	528217	746233	2281379	2878973	4510091	1820891	4563749	4045583	3232799	3344717	3580763	36000000
	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000	36000000

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 18. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3.
 See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc			5620071	3	mgc			5401857	3	mgc			6062379			
		1359937	1942207	2317927	5620071			995227	1901131	2505499	5401857			1951739	2041967	2068673	6062379
		2831347	1873357	915367	5620071			3310891	1800619	290347	5401857			2137727	2020793	1903859	6062379
		1428787	1804507	2386777	5620071			1095739	1700107	2606011	5401857			1972913	1999619	2089847	6062379
		5620071	5620071	5620071	5620071			5401857	5401857	5401857	5401857			6062379	6062379	6062379	6062379
3	mgc			6386181	3	mgc			6887019	3	mgc			5745021			
		1258097	2881031	2247053	6386181			1460653	2238277	3188089	6887019			1874987	1270421	2599613	5745021
		3117683	2128727	1139771	6386181			4023109	2295673	568237	6887019			2639633	1915007	1190381	5745021
		2010401	1376423	2999357	6386181			1403257	2353069	3130693	6887019			1230401	2559593	1955027	5745021
		6386181	6386181	6386181	6386181			6887019	6887019	6887019	6887019			5745021	5745021	5745021	5745021
3	mgc			5406351	3	mgc			5520369	3	mgc			6005361			
		958007	1850831	2597513	5406351			1335619	1926667	2258083	5520369			1338517	2442673	2224171	6005361
		3441623	1802117	162611	5406351			2762587	1840123	917659	5520369			2887441	2001787	1116133	6005361
		1006721	1753403	2646227	5406351			1422163	1753579	2344627	5520369			1779403	1560901	2665057	6005361
		5406351	5406351	5406351	5406351			5520369	5520369	5520369	5520369			6005361	6005361	6005361	6005361

Example 16. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

18	mgc																	18000054	
	201973	1953727	844309	246403	1914007	839599	1191313	1229773	578923	148549	1747087	1104373	896803	363379	1739827	1018873	191449	1789687	18000054
	1642339	1000003	357667	1593199	1000003	406807	387613	1000003	1612393	1955827	1000003	44179	1843027	1000003	156979	1770817	1000003	229189	18000054
	1155697	46279	1798033	1160407	85999	1753603	1421083	770233	808693	895633	252919	1851457	260179	1636627	1103203	210319	1808557	981133	18000054
	1293373	1085767	620869	833179	1589257	577573	132313	1735519	1132177	1480483	615919	903607	1360699	941617	697693	455473	1916737	627799	18000054
	327499	1000003	1672507	744397	1000003	1255609	1999867	1000003	139	423127	1000003	1576879	336997	1000003	1663009	1172329	1000003	827677	18000054
	1379137	914239	706633	1422433	410749	1166827	867829	264487	1867693	1096399	1384087	519523	1302313	1058389	639307	1372207	83269	1544533	18000054
	982453	788563	1228993	1754419	229837	1015753	1182403	1505599	312007	1001629	1093717	904663	1412863	776233	810913	935413	1327303	737293	18000054
	1246543	1000003	753463	261337	1000003	1738669	129607	1000003	1870399	903037	1000003	1096969	398053	1000003	1601953	801883	1000003	1198123	18000054
	771013	1211443	1017553	984253	1770169	245587	1687999	494407	817603	1095343	906289	998377	1189093	1223773	587143	1262713	672703	1064593	18000054
	668623	696793	1634593	118603	1801897	1079509	1799227	281719	919063	1716703	87583	1195723	1399543	1160443	440023	1224403	1217023	558583	18000054
	1965973	1000003	34033	1960909	1000003	39097	119839	1000003	1880167	479023	1000003	1520983	40483	1000003	1959523	334183	1000003	1665823	18000054
	365413	1303213	1331383	920497	198109	1881403	1080943	1718287	200779	804283	1912423	283303	1559983	839563	600463	1441423	782983	775603	18000054
	750487	1167709	1081813	496123	1445047	1058839	795727	646519	1557763	784153	1347397	868459	636073	1263079	1100857	975427	476479	1548103	18000054
	1331329	1000003	668677	1562719	1000003	437287	1762039	1000003	237967	1084309	1000003	915697	1464787	1000003	535219	1572679	1000003	427327	18000054
	918193	832297	1249519	941167	554959	1503883	442243	1353487	1204279	1131547	652609	1215853	899149	736927	1363933	451903	1523527	1024579	18000054
	164209	1823827	1011973	844183	1524073	631753	334429	1687657	977923	1131343	276553	1592113	1345207	340939	1313863	1586953	461407	951649	18000054
	1847767	1000003	152239	787573	1000003	1212433	1643497	1000003	356509	1460773	1000003	539233	968659	1000003	1031347	364699	1000003	1635307	18000054
	988033	176179	1835797	1368253	475933	1155823	1022083	312349	1665577	407893	1723453	868663	686143	1659067	654799	1048357	1538599	413053	18000054
	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 18. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 3. See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009			
	1293373	1085767	620869	3000009		833179	1589257	577573	3000009		896803	363379	1739827	3000009
	327499	1000003	1672507	3000009		744397	1000003	1255609	3000009		1843027	1000003	156979	3000009
	1379137	914239	706633	3000009		1422433	410749	1166827	3000009		260179	1636627	1103203	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009			
	1754419	229837	1015753	3000009		1799227	281719	919063	3000009		1399543	1160443	440023	3000009
	261337	1000003	1738669	3000009		119839	1000003	1880167	3000009		40483	1000003	1959523	3000009
	984253	1770169	245587	3000009		1080943	1718287	200779	3000009		1559983	839563	600463	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009	3	mgc		3000009			
	1001629	1093717	904663	3000009		1131343	276553	1592113	3000009		1586953	461407	951649	3000009
	903037	1000003	1096969	3000009		1460773	1000003	539233	3000009		364699	1000003	1635307	3000009
	1095343	906289	998377	3000009		407893	1723453	868663	3000009		1048357	1538599	413053	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009

Example 17. Different Sums Blocks of Order 6. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

18	mgc																		18000054
	1153849	407587	1152079	1121143	262807	265273	1234417	1080007	566107	1050817	874651	464263	2016787	1310809	1854109	427621	2057761	699967	18000054
	595873	1071223	321199	1133047	383023	858373	1295803	377617	1333621	423133	1379137	460951	2087689	765439	1764067	1024951	2023579	701329	18000054
	338563	390067	446893	1007353	1064179	1115683	541987	1204171	500953	1255801	552583	1214767	1631761	1449949	2040679	748339	1339069	1157257	18000054
	743923	717259	788173	666073	736987	710323	296797	1289557	236407	1520347	467197	1459957	516877	900169	343639	2445379	1888849	2272141	18000054
	341557	729943	1352227	102019	724303	1112689	608767	642163	1442527	314227	1114591	1147987	24889	2462479	1429651	1359367	326539	2764129	18000054
	1188973	1046659	302167	333103	1191439	300397	1292491	676747	1190647	705937	882103	522337	2089051	1478209	934909	2361397	731257	772231	18000054
	1448767	1167841	500239	2606497	2781469	1499521	1043293	1215919	1017889	554179	1168639	1000099	473191	516361	496333	250123	128053	131641	18000054
	2821957	1173589	1189417	2145361	2161189	512821	1608133	816469	603817	1396189	1183537	391873	185641	265711	167953	497281	399523	479593	18000054
	2425477	2102797	2373001	961777	1231981	909301	604063	950479	1199587	800419	1049527	1395943	334447	518083	442987	222247	147151	330787	18000054
	841879	1458031	1611451	1723327	1876747	2492899	425869	446197	229189	1770817	1553809	1574137	157273	305533	467557	197677	359701	507961	18000054
	630997	1935139	1495687	1839091	1399639	2703781	1318753	1786867	1967419	32587	213139	681253	311557	241141	251971	413263	424093	353677	18000054
	1835257	2166937	2834539	728281	553309	1886011	999907	784087	982117	1445827	831367	956713	533593	148873	168901	415111	537181	192043	18000054
	941971	713407	635737	466273	619573	256021	580939	862651	1609507	424537	1562131	1690009	852799	2077189	423439	804613	1833529	1645729	18000054
	415201	741337	580093	630901	469657	795793	1526401	802141	1743457	499801	1441117	716857	2111023	1414663	828637	1717129	1131103	434743	18000054
	499183	720211	258067	952927	490783	711811	1676911	1558177	1412539	830719	685081	566347	1442017	1502719	1223329	1322437	1043047	1103749	18000054
	739603	754903	793867	417127	456091	471391	444007	752359	840841	1402417	1490899	1799251	1435543	1906087	2369929	175837	639679	1110223	18000054
	82051	205537	789961	421033	1005457	1128943	1948267	1373839	489679	1753579	869419	294991	895879	268063	669637	1876129	2277703	1649887	18000054
	954973	497587	575257	744721	591421	269023	553249	1380607	633751	1818721	681127	1662319	900037	468577	2122327	1741153	712237	1692967	18000054
18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 18. The internal blocks are **different sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 6. See below few examples:

4	mgc					2908492		4	mgc					4000012			
		1071223	321199	1133047	383023	2908492				816469	603817	1396189	1183537	4000012			
		390067	446893	1007353	1064179	2908492				950479	1199587	800419	1049527	4000012			
		717259	788173	666073	736987	2908492				446197	229189	1770817	1553809	4000012			
		729943	1352227	102019	724303	2908492				1786867	1967419	32587	213139	4000012			
		2908492	2908492	2908492	2908492	2908492				4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012			
6	mgc						4362738		6	mgc						6000018	
		1153849	407587	1152079	1121143	262807	265273	4362738			1043293	1215919	1017889	554179	1168639	1000099	6000018
		595873	1071223	321199	1133047	383023	858373	4362738			1608133	816469	603817	1396189	1183537	391873	6000018
		338563	390067	446893	1007353	1064179	1115683	4362738			604063	950479	1199587	800419	1049527	1395943	6000018
		743923	717259	788173	666073	736987	710323	4362738			425869	446197	229189	1770817	1553809	1574137	6000018
		341557	729943	1352227	102019	724303	1112689	4362738			1318753	1786867	1967419	32587	213139	681253	6000018
		1188973	1046659	302167	333103	1191439	300397	4362738			999907	784087	982117	1445827	831367	956713	6000018
		4362738	4362738	4362738	4362738	4362738	4362738	4362738			6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018	6000018

Example 18. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 6. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

18	mgc																	18000054	
	1153849	407587	1152079	1121143	262807	265273	1234417	1080007	566107	1050817	874651	464263	2016787	1310809	1854109	427621	2057761	699967	18000054
	595873	1071223	321199	1133047	383023	858373	1295803	377617	1333621	423133	1379137	460951	2087689	765439	1764067	1024951	2023579	701329	18000054
	338563	390067	446893	1007353	1064179	1115683	541987	1204171	500953	1255801	552583	1214767	1631761	1449949	2040679	748339	1339069	1157257	18000054
	743923	717259	788173	666073	736987	710323	296797	1289557	236407	1520347	467197	1459957	516877	900169	343639	2445379	1888849	2272141	18000054
	341557	729943	1352227	102019	724303	1112689	608767	642163	1442527	314227	1114591	1147987	24889	2462479	1429651	1359367	326539	2764129	18000054
	1188973	1046659	302167	333103	1191439	300397	1292491	676747	1190647	705937	882103	522337	2089051	1478209	934909	2361397	731257	772231	18000054
	1448767	1167841	500239	2606497	2781469	1499521	1043293	1215919	1017889	554179	1168639	1000099	473191	516361	496333	250123	128053	131641	18000054
	2821957	1173589	1189417	2145361	2161189	512821	1608133	816469	603817	1396189	1183537	391873	185641	265711	167953	497281	399523	479593	18000054
	2425477	2102797	2373001	961777	1231981	909301	604063	950479	1199587	800419	1049527	1395943	334447	518083	442987	222247	147151	330787	18000054
	841879	1458031	1611451	1723327	1876747	2492899	425869	446197	229189	1770817	1553809	1574137	157273	305533	467557	197677	359701	507961	18000054
	630997	1935139	1495687	1839091	1399639	2703781	1318753	1786867	1967419	32587	213139	681253	311557	241141	251971	413263	424093	353677	18000054
	1835257	2166937	2834539	728281	553309	1886011	999907	784087	982117	1445827	831367	956713	533593	148873	168901	415111	537181	192043	18000054
	941971	713407	635737	466273	619573	256021	580939	862651	1609507	424537	1562131	1690009	852799	2077189	423439	804613	1833529	1645729	18000054
	415201	741337	580093	630901	469657	795793	1526401	802141	1743457	499801	1441117	716857	2111023	1414663	828637	1717129	1131103	434743	18000054
	499183	720211	258067	952927	490783	711811	1676911	1558177	1412539	830719	685081	566347	1442017	1502719	1223329	1322437	1043047	1103749	18000054
	739603	754903	793867	417127	456091	471391	444007	752359	840841	1402417	1490899	1799251	1435543	1906087	2369929	175837	639679	1110223	18000054
	82051	205537	789961	421033	1005457	1128943	1948267	1373839	489679	1753579	869419	294991	895879	268063	669637	1876129	2277703	1649887	18000054
	954973	497587	575257	744721	591421	269023	553249	1380607	633751	1818721	681127	1662319	900037	468577	2122327	1741153	712237	1692967	18000054
18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 18. The internal blocks are **equal sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 6.

Example 19. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 9. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

18	mgc																	18000054	
	1120663	625057	2004529	674953	444937	1549459	666019	430267	1484143	584281	375553	1293247	393517	250441	856759	1369099	874387	3002743	18000054
	2133949	1250083	366217	1764289	889783	15277	1678267	860143	42019	1459993	751027	42061	963481	500239	36997	3382387	1748743	115099	18000054
	495637	1875109	1379503	230107	1334629	1104613	236143	1290019	1054267	208807	1126501	917773	143719	750037	606961	494743	2623099	2128387	18000054
	460417	305119	1064653	934693	500029	1565287	1080973	694987	2393869	1516909	998989	3477259	750943	500413	1748653	2203	1201	3457	18000054
	1214299	610063	5827	1630597	1000003	369409	2702839	1389943	77047	3958069	1997719	37369	1997713	1000003	2293	3541	2287	1033	18000054
	155473	915007	759709	434719	1499977	1065313	386017	2084899	1698913	518179	2996449	2478529	251353	1499593	1249063	1117	3373	2371	18000054
	870013	570013	1979563	918913	555337	1856419	602839	374977	1271953	202519	125707	425563	1191577	750223	2557501	1034359	624517	2088061	18000054
	2249413	1139863	30313	2047729	1110223	172717	1419037	749923	80809	474307	251263	28219	2865691	1499767	133843	2302681	1248979	195277	18000054
	300163	1709713	1409713	364027	1665109	1301533	227893	1124869	897007	76963	376819	300007	442033	2249311	1807957	409897	1873441	1463599	18000054
	586633	377779	1301017	376759	250501	874267	1487401	872383	2873287	599983	387397	1336729	379699	250777	871681	1307107	862501	3004153	18000054
	1469527	755143	40759	998017	500509	3001	3130243	1744357	358471	1511449	774703	37957	992701	500719	8737	3421633	1724587	27541	18000054
	209269	1132507	923653	126751	750517	624259	615427	2616331	2001313	212677	1162009	949423	129757	750661	621739	445021	2586673	2142067	18000054
	1701307	994657	3271687	821833	500587	1677589	9337	5791	17239	1465567	974983	3409111	800923	500839	1698247	40627	25411	84319	18000054
	3559597	1989217	418837	1855759	1000003	144247	18691	10789	2887	3893431	1949887	6343	1897327	1000003	102679	93811	50119	6427	18000054
	706747	2983777	2277127	322417	1499419	1178173	4339	15787	12241	490663	2924791	2434207	301759	1499167	1199083	15919	74827	59611	18000054
	191977	127951	447019	1128553	749941	2619997	997099	622477	2115013	226201	137947	462109	1273957	749851	2474053	949303	612727	2113879	18000054
	510691	255649	607	2990941	1499497	8053	2362777	1244863	126949	511327	275419	39511	2699383	1499287	299191	2389879	1225303	60727	18000054
	64279	383347	319321	378997	2249053	1870441	374713	1867249	1492627	88729	412891	324637	524521	2248723	1724617	336727	1837879	1501303	18000054
	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054	18000054

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 18. The internal blocks are **equal sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 6.

Example 20. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

18	mgc																	9000000	
	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	9000000
	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	9000000
	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	9000000
	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	9000000
	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	9000000
	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	9000000
	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	9000000
	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	9000000
	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	9000000
	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	9000000
	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	9000000
	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	9000000
	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	9000000
	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	9000000
	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	9000000
	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	9000000
	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	9000000
	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	9000000
	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000	9000000

It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 18. The internal layer are also prime magic squares of orders 16, 14, 12, 10, 8, 6 and 4. It is the same as given in Example 3.9.

3.5 Prime Magic Squares of Order 19

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 19 with different representations.

Example 21. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

19	mgc																		39900057	
	2160217	3907949	2015107	1322953	1266079	227567	2383847	2067413	2698049	1994989	3796399	1179173	3292579	2421707	1708219	2910073	2014357	464773	2068607	39900057
	3131017	3071897	2840657	937577	1604573	79103	3103579	2954417	861493	2439893	2131417	3576323	2108737	1634603	3961057	1956529	1293917	1144279	1068989	39900057
	349963	1964063	1597397	1291163	2114771	1754497	2407549	3894523	1075241	2140847	2704469	1113221	1616597	2631029	1961537	2714111	2483093	2235943	3850043	39900057
	3150197	715223	2185151	1667777	1150403	4825549	2685523	545497	3602747	1973519	344291	3304757	1786949	269141	2907803	2386247	1864691	3484783	1049809	39900057
	455333	3813463	1220783	2044391	1738157	1476523	2963497	3616549	1242569	1806191	2871797	942869	1957301	2460677	2289401	2058383	2810957	386543	3744673	39900057
	3806749	3263627	1666081	1143049	2203153	1762477	2285683	3158791	1462999	1012831	2228167	1709671	2380387	3192439	2317067	1868561	3108689	936379	393257	39900057
	1090027	1295113	2207833	1670761	1133689	3798631	2402317	1006003	2333167	1567999	802831	3910267	2427499	944731	3223061	2431439	1639817	2904893	3109979	39900057
	1639223	3087457	1138369	2198473	1675441	1645843	2518951	3042157	907831	2123167	1672999	1662559	2474611	3145327	1754189	2994317	2545811	1112549	2560783	39900057
	1916573	133439	1998089	1673447	2491031	2648593	1579009	3759757	1516847	1163993	2130251	1027391	1733873	1852817	2202929	1775219	3946799	4066567	2283433	39900057
	1108259	1352167	2547131	2054189	1561247	3773617	2662453	1551289	2217101	1603697	990293	2363453	1538027	712601	4385519	2641649	897779	2847839	3091747	39900057
	1152233	3206303	1617347	2434931	2110289	1565149	3745897	2676313	1077143	2043401	1690547	1223237	1342181	2048663	1336499	3508079	3080369	993703	3047773	39900057
	275699	1710529	1683497	1306373	2616461	682751	976991	872441	1462319	1631771	2759507	2284691	3591143	5556449	1538917	1762177	2774557	2489477	3924307	39900057
	2315897	2399477	2801741	1868777	935813	1033751	844061	654371	3248387	1951199	654011	7082519	3810761	539003	3260857	2025217	789577	1800529	1884109	39900057
	2281039	392467	1121093	2431181	2054057	815681	711131	1005371	1142891	2270627	2440079	2065073	4030379	5336831	1275877	2288257	2511517	3807539	1918967	39900057
	3766117	1840057	2485421	3196499	4033613	1214971	2270071	2231941	2194883	3140369	4875551	909299	596927	1304111	946823	718379	1381187	2359949	433889	39900057
	2479409	739649	4786703	3238511	1690319	2922631	1905661	888691	6084269	3403601	722933	1331591	936779	541967	1449827	1015463	581099	3460357	1720597	39900057
	4127897	3659393	2443409	3280523	3991601	1579381	1541251	2596351	1931651	3666833	4612319	569447	1276631	964259	649739	1312547	1084103	540613	72109	39900057
	2562809	3055727	1359349	3262429	2595433	4120903	1096427	1245589	3338513	1760113	2068589	623683	2091269	2565403	238949	2243477	2906089	1128109	1637197	39900057
	2131399	292057	2184899	2877053	2933927	3972439	1816159	2132593	1501957	2205017	403607	3020833	907427	1778299	2491787	1289933	2185649	3735233	2039789	39900057
	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057	39900057

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 19 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.1.

Example 22. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

19	mgc																		19000057	
	1583899	410359	382567	54277	1869859	1010473	1066399	1074919	919249	1142599	677683	36313	1688803	1510897	997453	589327	1558759	1034809	1391413	19000057
	1927729	1176433	603769	1917397	1998343	99817	1345453	102367	1720189	834859	1474069	1491643	628057	442579	170389	1084459	818359	1091869	72277	19000057
	1276183	1310137	1779109	370837	850063	1541809	636817	821383	881437	1407409	711163	582949	1892167	524893	1818703	41443	1139863	689869	723823	19000057
	556537	1402603	70957	1000003	1929049	279577	1000003	1720429	829729	1000003	1170277	941947	1000003	1058059	321163	1000003	1678843	597403	1443469	19000057
	754417	1389559	1149943	1629169	220897	1178623	1363189	458197	1288843	592597	1118569	1475113	107839	1417057	860143	1958563	181303	610447	1245589	19000057
	100699	1025047	547453	1569649	882907	1116889	457117	1426003	1029433	63667	1906909	899917	1439239	660853	1404883	702529	892597	974959	1899307	19000057
	209857	1369483	1335457	1000003	664549	1309117	1000003	690889	1877479	1000003	122527	760939	1000003	1239067	487717	1000003	1512289	630523	1790149	19000057
	1764733	543883	1117099	430357	1452553	574003	1542889	883117	93097	1936339	970573	1339153	560767	1100089	1107409	1297477	595123	1456123	235273	19000057
	1571329	186679	606379	1919677	473953	837139	1999297	163573	1147717	1265119	587173	1406857	734389	858763	740023	1389139	870847	1813327	428677	19000057
	329143	1135903	867577	1000003	1132429	326437	1000003	1673569	439459	1000003	1560547	451909	1000003	1548097	1130827	1000003	869179	864103	1670863	19000057
	357229	1026547	1526053	80329	1393627	1836433	709	1162867	1412833	734887	852289	1141243	1265617	593149	1129159	610867	1259983	973459	1642777	19000057
	993397	326149	323509	1790707	885793	804157	525979	1669873	600403	1839427	560179	637543	1630927	731539	1123483	1353433	523093	1673857	1006609	19000057
	727843	1874143	1562287	1000003	437719	1865719	1000003	134287	959779	1000003	1040227	1093999	1000003	906007	399613	1000003	1600393	125863	1272163	19000057
	905083	783829	1114213	209299	1676497	330133	1474027	1195849	1439827	160579	1399603	1268467	369079	1362463	1476913	646573	876523	1216177	1094923	19000057
	193507	792307	1055863	131143	1813003	1282543	1009483	707983	343333	1914163	742513	920833	1467589	611587	1254733	994069	751207	1207699	1806499	19000057
	1773649	1382023	1757143	1000003	242863	425443	1000003	1574563	1399183	1000003	600823	690757	1000003	1309249	496477	1000003	1503529	617983	226357	19000057
	1663303	367189	187003	1868863	944143	1292023	990523	717463	1257493	85843	1656673	1388419	532417	1079173	1248799	1005937	745273	1632817	336703	19000057
	1702927	908137	1396237	82609	1663	1900189	654553	1897639	279817	1165147	525937	508363	1371949	1557427	1829617	915547	1181647	823573	297079	19000057
	608593	1589647	1617439	1945729	130147	989533	933607	925087	1080757	857407	1322323	1963693	311203	489109	1002553	1410679	441247	965197	416107	19000057
	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 19 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 3. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.2.

Example 23. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Cocentric Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

19	mgc																		174342347	
	17272043	9717467	17167883	6103397	920957	11037557	15390269	3409337	7076603	16301933	2121767	13290779	3315317	11625983	9747233	7471889	13294727	8505113	572093	174342347
	2941073	4579637	17017457	10557359	11742989	8459813	4395869	328277	2110217	17895089	2432093	2204507	9744797	15177089	4624787	16038839	15372779	13308923	15410753	174342347
	11876087	17628263	9218123	9237923	9238193	9252863	9236963	8970503	9003803	9004103	9027533	9001523	9277043	9290843	9293363	9296123	9289793	723563	6475739	174342347
	3255179	15976589	9237533	9242483	9223733	9244223	9236093	9002993	9002003	8994053	9008423	8999993	9290123	9294713	9270893	9302693	9288743	2375237	15096647	174342347
	978269	7424909	9238703	9238553	9236813	9235073	9234923	9006953	9007913	9001493	8995073	8996033	9293663	9297413	9289433	9281453	9285203	10926917	17373557	174342347
	329009	6852917	9253043	9229403	9249893	9231143	9220583	9025553	8994563	9008933	9000983	8977433	9297263	9276173	9307973	9284153	9281603	11498909	18022817	174342347
	12539333	5636789	9236663	9235703	9235433	9220763	9255503	9001463	8999183	8998883	8975453	9032483	9289073	9288023	9285503	9282743	9301823	12715037	5812493	174342347
	9949169	6271127	9208553	9232073	9232673	9239303	9230063	9140093	9178073	9178733	9206663	9176003	9074783	9124133	9126983	9166943	9123623	12080699	8402657	174342347
	4329737	18328547	9230183	9229973	9224753	9230873	9226883	9177293	9176813	9163403	9187523	9174533	9124043	9125393	9116033	9128453	9122543	23279	14022089	174342347
	9564143	9831863	9232793	9229433	9228533	9227633	9224273	9190073	9186623	9175913	9165203	9161753	9132323	9126353	9123293	9120233	9114263	8519963	8787683	174342347
	10972373	3836867	9244133	9226193	9232313	9227093	9212933	9196283	9164303	9188423	9175013	9155543	9162353	9118133	9130553	9121193	9084233	14514959	7379453	174342347
	9663527	9023327	9227003	9224993	9224393	9217763	9248513	9175823	9173753	9173093	9145163	9211733	9122963	9122453	9119603	9079643	9171803	9328499	8688299	174342347
	2297903	3930257	9046523	9064193	9064613	9073193	9063443	9319703	9351383	9352253	9377603	9350723	9096203	9118493	9118793	9123833	9117743	14421569	16053923	174342347
	14275799	15213923	9063623	9068483	9042353	9076343	9061163	9350813	9356453	9332423	9362123	9349853	9118223	9118853	9104453	9121733	9111803	3137903	4076027	174342347
	2098553	7408007	9069503	9070253	9062393	9054533	9055283	9354893	9356003	9350333	9344663	9345773	9119333	9117893	9115013	9112133	9110693	10943819	16253273	174342347
	9788069	15467939	9070973	9048443	9082433	9056303	9053813	9376313	9338543	9368243	9344213	9324353	9129023	9108293	9125573	9111173	9101003	2883887	8563757	174342347
	16694129	3536657	9061343	9060593	9060173	9051593	9078263	9349943	9349283	9348413	9323063	9380963	9112283	9111533	9111233	9106193	9133823	14815169	1657697	174342347
	17738219	5042903	1334369	7794467	6608837	9892013	13955957	18023549	16241609	456737	15919733	16147319	8607029	3174737	13727039	2312987	2979047	13772189	613607	174342347
	17779733	8634359	1183943	12248429	17430869	7314269	2961557	14942489	11275223	2049893	16230059	5061047	15036509	6725843	8604593	10879937	5057099	9846713	1079783	174342347
	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347	174342347

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 19 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **different sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 5. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.3.

Example 24. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Concentric Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

19	mgc																		19000057	
	156799	411127	1588393	1105009	1067749	1404919	1106977	778717	1147213	1368163	1642093	1520473	1228789	327499	1135327	691399	1530037	418837	370537	19000057
	846247	316957	1056793	121309	1211059	1799599	310729	1038259	500839	809983	662107	1267009	1990327	1254637	1936609	88903	686143	1948789	1153759	19000057
	1491493	901339	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	1098667	508513	19000057
	554179	1974787	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	25219	1445827	19000057
	47017	1710517	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	289489	1952989	19000057
	56929	272179	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	1727827	1943077	19000057
	1826947	152443	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	1847563	173059	19000057
	1110367	643507	1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	1356499	889639	19000057
	268693	1721449	1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	278557	1731313	19000057
	1807249	1049479	566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	950527	192757	19000057
	1864399	1569703	1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	430303	135607	19000057
	1411573	1457059	214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	542947	588433	19000057
	1913473	1003819	1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	996187	86533	19000057
	1045153	1370977	851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	629029	954853	19000057
	393109	230467	1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	1769539	1606897	19000057
	1389727	1704103	789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	295903	610279	19000057
	115327	870049	18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	1129957	1884679	19000057
	1071907	51217	943213	1878697	788947	200407	1689277	961747	1499167	1190023	1337899	732997	9679	745369	63397	1911103	1313863	1683049	928099	19000057
	1629469	1588879	411613	894997	932257	595087	893029	1221289	852793	631843	357913	479533	771217	1672507	864679	1308607	469969	1581169	1843207	19000057
	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 19 embedded with a prime magic square of order 15 with **equal sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 5. The prime magic square of order 15 is the same as given in Example 3.4.

Example 25. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

19	mgc																		19000057		
	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	19000057	
	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	19000057	
	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	19000057	
	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	19000057	
	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	19000057	
	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	19000057	
	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	19000057	
	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	19000057	
	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	19000057	
	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	19000057	
	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	19000057	
	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	19000057	
	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	19000057	
	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	19000057	
	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	19000057	
	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19000057	
	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	19000057	
	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	19000057	
	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	19000057	
	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057	19000057

It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 19. The internal layer are also prime magic squares of orders 17, 15, 13, 11, 9, 7, 5 and 3. It is the same as given in Example 3.14.

3.6 Prime Magic Squares of Order 20

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 20 with different representations.

Example 26. Different Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			42000060	
	2192093	1704559	1673393	1903103	2500417	1422857	1625831	2368187	1623907	2638931	2283403	2103163	2157821	2574977	3042367	2778023	1945969	2163107	1412219	1885733	42000060
	2163281	1531253	2057431	1721183	2297747	1867211	1898107	1854227	2397007	2311417	2150671	1790309	2817887	2951731	2604521	2179049	1665137	2154533	2076967	1510391	42000060
	1667833	2062673	1821791	1920851	1492661	2024531	2127443	2272657	2321959	2089039	2098277	2140129	2087993	1681157	3315779	3468259	2274653	1923059	1252469	1956847	42000060
	1449941	2174663	1920533	1928011	1626467	2602693	2265911	1422221	2306531	1610017	2117053	2615803	3489487	3345323	1590521	2127857	1521269	1166329	2665373	2054057	42000060
	1554227	1776433	2153699	2302757	2143969	1499011	1579321	2346191	2572133	2334557	2190329	1961857	2941223	2287421	2083009	3223799	2085929	1546453	1538441	1879301	42000060
	1400417	2349209	2323121	1714369	1884907	1469081	2115853	2098651	2228333	2179609	2360363	2290571	2901989	2378443	3215231	2039789	1360349	2217143	2018573	1454059	42000060
	2404931	733697	2381089	2267399	1641077	1207909	2775649	1943857	2777311	3255557	1263347	1762661	2796707	2200889	2740889	2796967	1709243	1257647	1556761	2526473	42000060
	2427541	2927777	929207	1502591	1898539	3392491	1097669	1179793	1481099	1289153	3244837	3043787	1895533	3668699	2496323	2474897	1894603	2028881	1936349	1190291	42000060
	2755421	2544797	2456243	2851111	1976687	1909109	2759069	2763931	1187629	1836287	1499123	2274149	2236823	1387069	2038969	1285351	1874857	2412439	1516609	2434387	42000060
	2527961	2828641	2296433	2954537	2110321	2503559	2812967	1981949	1740731	2096867	1294561	1665029	1794769	2007301	1301171	1844971	1705273	2293273	1884409	2355337	42000060
	2805703	2941541	2540957	2319371	2103389	613499	3478771	3213137	2104607	1464257	1941503	1286821	1642939	3088009	551731	1665533	1488343	749677	3310933	2689339	42000060
	2518487	2292593	3313939	2482553	3218399	4382629	357989	1449779	1764221	1399777	2062001	1571189	1273681	465833	3056341	2152357	3169819	2782903	1526341	759229	42000060
	1802621	1232171	1868371	1624913	2373989	1884293	1330943	2067019	1883627	2815171	2885261	2287409	2089567	2453027	2347313	2510537	2419181	1687381	2385499	2051767	42000060
	1038253	1494347	2033573	1961903	2410519	1376723	1961549	1907453	2158061	3044651	1888063	2780693	2642537	2225057	2370103	2162747	2089093	1565911	2486623	2402201	42000060
	1306979	489367	2510789	2220941	1709189	2465129	1852843	1629083	2648911	2515127	2423627	2283803	2707349	2558813	2246471	1887811	2596873	2566757	1924537	1455661	42000060
	2380223	3312191	115343	720319	1162547	1930099	2510909	2052689	3180869	1496519	2674517	2519563	1960991	2163547	2436557	2839349	1438681	2723779	1747169	2634199	42000060
	2942749	1974851	2170291	2516257	2395307	2253193	2278343	2522393	1530839	1934117	1730437	2427731	1368803	1059017	1058027	1076917	2642201	2231609	2894929	2992049	42000060
	1859281	2971537	2125567	2647763	2143733	2597897	2288807	2418799	1642049	2253289	2143019	1584767	901907	968917	979787	1712153	2511011	2545237	2652011	3052529	42000060
	2130367	2290573	2216471	2966737	1808843	1536683	3025849	3077861	1740359	342497	2884319	2655949	1275457	1489463	1124597	673247	2210837	1719989	3843551	2986411	42000060
	2671751	2367187	3091819	1473391	3101353	3061463	1856237	1430183	2709877	3093221	865349	954677	1016597	1045367	1400353	1100447	3396739	4263953	1370297	1729799	42000060
	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060	42000060

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 20. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 4.
 See below few examples of order 4:

4	mgc					7473148	4	mgc					7917292	4	mgc					8649404
		2192093	1704559	1673393	1903103	7473148			2500417	1422857	1625831	2368187	7917292			1623907	2638931	2283403	2103163	8649404
		2163281	1531253	2057431	1721183	7473148			2297747	1867211	1898107	1854227	7917292			2397007	2311417	2150671	1790309	8649404
		1667833	2062673	1821791	1920851	7473148			1492661	2024531	2127443	2272657	7917292			2321959	2089039	2098277	2140129	8649404
		1449941	2174663	1920533	1928011	7473148			1626467	2602693	2265911	1422221	7917292			2306531	1610017	2117053	2615803	8649404
		7473148	7473148	7473148	7473148	7473148			7917292	7917292	7917292	7917292	7917292			8649404	8649404	8649404	8649404	8649404
4	mgc					7787116	4	mgc					7568492	4	mgc					9058876
		1554227	1776433	2153699	2302757	7787116			2143969	1499011	1579321	2346191	7568492			2572133	2334557	2190329	1961857	9058876
		1400417	2349209	2323121	1714369	7787116			1884907	1469081	2115853	2098651	7568492			2228333	2179609	2360363	2290571	9058876
		2404931	733697	2381089	2267399	7787116			1641077	1207909	2775649	1943857	7568492			2777311	3255557	1263347	1762661	9058876
		2427541	2927777	929207	1502591	7787116			1898539	3392491	1097669	1179793	7568492			1481099	1289153	3244837	3043787	9058876
		7787116	7787116	7787116	7787116	7787116			7568492	7568492	7568492	7568492	7568492			9058876	9058876	9058876	9058876	9058876
4	mgc					10607572	4	mgc					9408796	4	mgc					6797188
		2755421	2544797	2456243	2851111	10607572			1976687	1909109	2759069	2763931	9408796			1187629	1836287	1499123	2274149	6797188
		2527961	2828641	2296433	2954537	10607572			2110321	2503559	2812967	1981949	9408796			1740731	2096867	1294561	1665029	6797188
		2805703	2941541	2540957	2319371	10607572			2103389	613499	3478771	3213137	9408796			2104607	1464257	1941503	1286821	6797188
		2518487	2292593	3313939	2482553	10607572			3218399	4382629	357989	1449779	9408796			1764221	1399777	2062001	1571189	6797188
		10607572	10607572	10607572	10607572	10607572			9408796	9408796	9408796	9408796	9408796			6797188	6797188	6797188	6797188	6797188

Example 27. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			20000060	
	1448989	621337	1378669	551017	1101253	889879	1110127	898753	1164967	918193	1081813	835039	1172467	922333	1077673	827539	1177843	866953	1133053	822163	20000060
	603817	1823149	176857	1396189	907723	1746127	253879	1092283	849019	1682413	317593	1150987	862669	1674913	325093	1137337	881233	1669537	330469	1118773	20000060
	129127	1454059	545947	1870879	281539	1137883	862123	1718467	308359	1169713	830293	1691647	291349	1173853	826153	1708657	272179	1178623	821383	1727827	20000060
	1818079	101467	1898539	181927	1709497	226123	1773883	290509	1677667	229693	1770313	322339	1673527	228913	1771093	326479	1668757	284899	1715107	331249	20000060
	1752397	251359	1748647	247609	1781173	258109	1741897	218833	1638913	329347	1670659	361093	1678639	354877	1645129	321367	1682389	355513	1644493	317617	20000060
	307423	1877353	122653	1692583	283303	1848577	151429	1716703	401053	1903339	96667	1598953	331777	1863613	136393	1668229	370537	1859863	140143	1629469	20000060
	80629	1770187	229819	1919377	90403	1784617	215389	1909603	94327	1676533	323473	1905679	126037	1678693	321313	1873969	89137	1684303	315703	1910869	20000060
	1859563	101113	1898893	140443	1845133	108709	1891297	154873	1865719	90793	1909213	134287	1863559	102829	1897177	136447	1857949	100333	1899673	142057	20000060
	1782289	235273	1764733	217717	1788433	209857	1790149	211573	1325557	661099	1338907	674449	1364617	666889	1333117	635389	1387417	652369	1347637	612589	20000060
	258127	1866973	133033	1741879	243829	1860829	139177	1756177	692239	1873507	126499	1307767	648259	1834447	165559	1351747	665719	1811647	188359	1334287	20000060
	93553	1783219	216787	1906453	108517	1790029	209977	1891489	122209	1339057	660949	1877797	155689	1367617	632389	1844317	136399	1388587	611419	1863607	20000060
	1866043	114547	1885459	133963	1859233	139297	1860709	140773	1860007	126349	1873657	139999	1831447	131059	1868947	168559	1810477	147409	1852597	189529	20000060
	1175569	836863	1163143	824437	1200349	861823	1138183	799657	1219843	857407	1142599	780163	1674997	288913	1711093	325009	1732267	260419	1739587	267739	20000060
	867487	1805653	194353	1132519	878833	1780873	219133	1121173	868957	1761379	238627	1131049	295129	1887433	112573	1704877	322549	1830163	169843	1677457	20000060
	163573	1187839	812167	1836433	150247	1210639	789367	1849759	176629	1246639	753367	1823377	181219	1713763	286243	1818787	126493	1743727	256279	1873513	20000060
	1793383	169657	1830349	206623	1770583	146677	1853329	229423	1734583	134587	1865419	265423	1848667	109903	1890103	151339	1818703	165703	1834303	181303	20000060
	1742989	299287	1700719	257017	1522483	474583	1525423	477523	1528237	461017	1538989	471769	1540879	493573	1506433	459127	1546759	457813	1542193	453247	20000060
	301867	1820509	179497	1698139	472057	1868983	131023	1527949	475669	1863229	136777	1524337	471217	1850587	149419	1528789	460063	1844707	155299	1539943	20000060
	152077	1760419	239587	1847929	137413	1523407	476599	1862593	140983	1536343	463663	1859023	137659	1541209	458797	1862347	149503	1547779	452227	1850503	20000060
	1803079	119797	1880209	196927	1868059	133039	1866967	131947	1855123	139423	1860583	144883	1850257	114643	1885363	149749	1843687	149713	1850293	156319	20000060
	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 20. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 4. See below few examples of order 4:

4	mgc				4000012	4	mgc				4000012
	1101253	889879	1110127	898753	4000012		1528237	461017	1538989	471769	4000012
	907723	1746127	253879	1092283	4000012		475669	1863229	136777	1524337	4000012
	281539	1137883	862123	1718467	4000012		140983	1536343	463663	1859023	4000012
	1709497	226123	1773883	290509	4000012		1855123	139423	1860583	144883	4000012
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012
4	mgc				4000012	4	mgc				4000012
	1325557	661099	1338907	674449	4000012		1172467	922333	1077673	827539	4000012
	692239	1873507	126499	1307767	4000012		862669	1674913	325093	1137337	4000012
	122209	1339057	660949	1877797	4000012		291349	1173853	826153	1708657	4000012
	1860007	126349	1873657	139999	4000012		1673527	228913	1771093	326479	4000012
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012
4	mgc				4000012	4	mgc				4000012
	1732267	260419	1739587	267739	4000012		1674997	288913	1711093	325009	4000012
	322549	1830163	169843	1677457	4000012		295129	1887433	112573	1704877	4000012
	126493	1743727	256279	1873513	4000012		181219	1713763	286243	1818787	4000012
	1818703	165703	1834303	181303	4000012		1848667	109903	1890103	151339	4000012
	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012		4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012	4000012

Example 28. Different Sums Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			20000060
929323	861937	1377967	1497019	1245169	315361	385279	767527	735157	1071121	1194163	460087	1597873	1614391	1859071	225769	959083	848203	522757	1532803	20000060
1846849	756703	1105537	1684609	517717	864439	554467	225931	1184269	445339	2257117	1461667	667141	1906543	433117	1380517	502429	631717	1319023	254929	20000060
1400353	2110189	1182283	254377	964213	591391	1284691	654889	25087	718387	1328491	1789993	1345117	900241	1361743	1121203	1634317	817723	1129	514243	20000060
615493	679957	1259029	1607863	1749073	1264597	125509	1083847	755311	45181	1114651	783691	2023093	1228567	1575583	1258483	316423	1003729	1133017	376963	20000060
1119397	1502629	986599	867547	1435243	238657	924499	542251	574621	994417	831163	2230147	1092361	1075843	1496071	102643	676363	787243	1112689	1409677	20000060
1280113	922717	951151	695257	665947	1349287	720289	913279	442753	120157	1314127	809587	1581037	1475827	1273687	983119	1239319	1570879	613141	1078387	20000060
287611	741337	533821	1433953	1518463	380803	753847	431449	942163	1037503	1880947	1601107	722539	1548913	700759	1529761	936379	334021	2020507	664177	20000060
1457503	1595653	903037	210421	348571	283519	897469	709153	520837	1134787	1402153	1238659	1290853	1343047	1179553	1341187	2181097	1096969	12841	852751	20000060
349831	372121	1272253	1064737	1456243	234007	476143	986857	664459	1184299	549019	1032793	1859167	980599	2032687	515227	173431	1859917	1257559	1678711	20000060
1140127	883357	854923	1110817	525961	1298149	698017	505027	975553	69019	1308019	1772119	1000669	1105879	1267579	1115551	954619	623059	1580797	1210819	20000060
1125343	1096189	1114159	483757	1347667	1000507	1222561	1340653	589207	897907	247309	366907	1304599	1217809	1812571	421639	1118629	370009	1450249	1472389	20000060
1100857	1702177	710089	688003	965989	583537	1051957	745981	1232563	1436797	1123219	1608379	598219	762919	856459	1538917	970969	404167	1524613	394249	20000060
1731397	19249	1033423	2047597	335449	1208833	1190773	1010167	829561	811501	1655089	144379	989839	1835299	324589	531919	1520227	966583	412939	1401247	20000060
490339	1378843	1356757	364669	1576507	1135531	787771	1274353	968377	884803	1756471	1216759	1381459	371299	223207	1879663	408553	1528999	962197	53503	20000060
719179	970657	952687	1583089	941503	1122427	797773	679681	1431127	1019827	167107	1612771	675079	761869	1732369	460777	814537	1563157	482917	1511527	20000060
666727	318247	1147387	1400107	873877	1491157	2069449	2015347	501829	2051233	407713	388897	473497	124309	476599	1044367	386161	1216807	1471117	1475233	20000060
507919	1090519	444289	1108999	1254619	2131099	1212649	1555507	2109253	1120507	217429	261223	284857	576529	530977	1431733	1868527	355723	1131961	805741	20000060
1019839	899749	881269	862789	742699	2421253	2522407	1625803	729199	830353	291997	689509	374203	58897	456409	1194343	382171	1118737	1855303	1043131	20000060
1323199	653539	1318249	672019	439339	885133	1142353	1696099	2038957	2366473	682069	171877	463549	487183	66337	1161001	1105513	1881751	368947	1076473	20000060
888661	1444291	615151	362431	1095811	1200373	1182157	1236259	2749777	1760449	271807	359509	274909	624097	340693	762241	1851313	1020667	766357	1193107	20000060
20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 20. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 5.
 See below few examples of order 5:

3	mgc				3546849				3	mgc				2127459		
		756703	1105537	1684609	3546849						753847	431449	942163	2127459		
		2110189	1182283	254377	3546849						897469	709153	520837	2127459		
		679957	1259029	1607863	3546849						476143	986857	664459	2127459		
		3546849	3546849	3546849	3546849						2127459	2127459	2127459	2127459		
5	mgc					5911415			5	mgc					3545765	
		929323	861937	1377967	1497019	1245169	5911415				1349287	720289	913279	442753	120157	3545765
		1846849	756703	1105537	1684609	517717	5911415				380803	753847	431449	942163	1037503	3545765
		1400353	2110189	1182283	254377	964213	5911415				283519	897469	709153	520837	1134787	3545765
		615493	679957	1259029	1607863	1749073	5911415				234007	476143	986857	664459	1184299	3545765
		1119397	1502629	986599	867547	1435243	5911415				1298149	698017	505027	975553	69019	3545765
		5911415	5911415	5911415	5911415	5911415	5911415				3545765	3545765	3545765	3545765	3545765	3545765
3	mgc				1122609				3	mgc				3290907		
		261223	284857	576529	1122609						936379	334021	2020507	3290907		
		689509	374203	58897	1122609						2181097	1096969	12841	3290907		
		171877	463549	487183	1122609						173431	1859917	1257559	3290907		
		1122609	1122609	1122609	1122609						3290907	3290907	3290907	3290907		
5	mgc					1871015			5	mgc					5484845	
		407713	388897	473497	124309	476599	1871015				983119	1239319	1570879	613141	1078387	5484845
		217429	261223	284857	576529	530977	1871015				1529761	936379	334021	2020507	664177	5484845
		291997	689509	374203	58897	456409	1871015				1341187	2181097	1096969	12841	852751	5484845
		682069	171877	463549	487183	66337	1871015				515227	173431	1859917	1257559	1678711	5484845
		271807	359509	274909	624097	340693	1871015				1115551	954619	623059	1580797	1210819	5484845
		1871015	1871015	1871015	1871015	1871015	1871015				5484845	5484845	5484845	5484845	5484845	5484845

Example 29. *Equal Sums Blocks of Order 5.* Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			20000060
1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	1401217	929323	509449	605497	1554529	20000060
1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	1293967	1059433	805249	1135327	706039	20000060
1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	1640467	1075897	1000003	924109	359539	20000060
481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	218887	864679	1194757	940573	1781119	20000060
284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	445477	1070683	1490557	1394509	598789	20000060
1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	1687297	727939	447883	345979	1790917	20000060
1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	848923	963667	390499	1645843	1151083	20000060
566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	310627	1682179	1000003	317827	1689379	20000060
1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	1944079	354163	1609507	1036339	55927	20000060
214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	209089	1272067	1552123	1654027	312709	20000060
1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	1187749	495973	828169	620647	1867477	20000060
851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	511867	852289	941167	1206553	1488139	20000060
1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	1562593	1354267	1000003	645739	437413	20000060
789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	1605277	793453	1058839	1147717	394729	20000060
18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	132529	1504033	1171837	1379359	812257	20000060
1613707	263737	549517	945787	1627267	1010263	577807	833719	720547	1857679	1597243	511963	253879	644383	1992547	1519657	349579	938857	433369	1758553	20000060
1066063	750943	523207	1725859	933943	659299	729367	966139	1304503	1340707	1495867	1635583	697693	666733	504139	758929	1459099	250057	1290853	1241077	20000060
1370227	1974919	1000003	25087	629779	1302919	1575139	1000003	424867	697087	1450453	31153	1000003	1968853	549553	1422973	831757	1000003	1168249	577033	20000060
577279	274147	1476799	1249063	1422727	1885207	695503	1033867	1270639	114799	448993	1333273	1302313	364423	1551013	1057003	709153	1749949	540907	943003	20000060
372739	1736269	1450489	1054219	386299	142327	1422199	1166287	1279459	989743	7459	1488043	1746127	1355623	402763	241453	1650427	1061149	1566637	480349	20000060
20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 20. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 5. See below few examples of order 5:

3	mgc			3000009				3	mgc			3000009		
	1176787	464419	1358803	3000009					852289	941167	1206553	3000009		
	1182019	1000003	817987	3000009					1354267	1000003	645739	3000009		
	641203	1535587	823219	3000009					793453	1058839	1147717	3000009		
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009					3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		
5	mgc							5	mgc				5000015	
	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	5000015			1187749	495973	828169	620647	1867477	5000015
	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	5000015			511867	852289	941167	1206553	1488139	5000015
	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	5000015			1562593	1354267	1000003	645739	437413	5000015
	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	5000015			1605277	793453	1058839	1147717	394729	5000015
	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	5000015			132529	1504033	1171837	1379359	812257	5000015
	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015			5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015	5000015

Example 30. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 10. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			20000060	
	1576747	1063747	657439	335953	733963	1624963	569053	1626613	1299979	511573	181927	1244197	1145077	1483507	950149	787519	482689	998443	934033	1792489	20000060
	1009207	1348987	1041949	958057	651019	796339	1065109	934897	1203667	990799	1596139	1098439	513319	1486687	901567	804337	560179	1439827	1195669	403867	20000060
	1362637	1007557	567829	1432177	992449	1324117	672703	1327303	675889	637369	1652719	1308607	1124083	875923	691399	556849	1156699	843307	1443157	347287	20000060
	458377	667819	941167	1058839	1332187	817087	406573	1593433	1182919	1541629	1225879	968197	1597753	402253	1031809	1534207	856417	1143589	465799	774127	20000060
	493393	975649	1449067	550939	1024357	1062469	1855627	144379	937537	1506613	1192579	624769	764857	1235149	1375237	1104619	1426717	573289	895387	807427	20000060
	1072363	987013	1164343	835663	1012993	1110643	1007089	992917	889363	927643	1461697	1543999	437953	1562053	456007	498643	443419	1556587	1501363	538309	20000060
	613969	441703	731593	1268413	1558303	622849	1555717	444289	1377157	1386037	590797	966817	697267	1302739	1033189	965047	1573933	426073	1034959	1409209	20000060
	353527	1226977	374287	1625719	773029	727123	1126963	873043	1272883	1646479	1178557	1060519	1812589	187417	939487	1247479	783733	1216273	752527	821449	20000060
	1571377	1344319	1729789	270217	655687	1539397	310243	1689763	460609	428629	712219	428677	1052203	947803	1571329	1288843	1198927	801079	711163	1287787	20000060
	1488433	936259	1342567	1664053	1266043	375043	1430953	373393	700027	423259	207517	755809	854929	516499	1049857	1212487	1517317	1001563	1065973	1818079	20000060
	739723	874267	738643	1656427	695917	1670419	1032643	1053757	302287	1235947	1404643	670903	1524409	1002343	319927	1544563	478963	1489393	846229	718657	20000060
	475897	1416799	1490353	509653	583207	1189897	556483	1443523	810109	1524109	1294597	1470613	1356877	643129	529393	775267	1551619	448387	1224739	705409	20000060
	1696327	909247	607357	1392649	1090759	695503	1467673	532333	1304503	303679	727459	749167	1195849	804157	1250839	1462939	1264177	735829	537067	1272547	20000060
	715999	861439	1211629	788377	1138567	1217509	1760467	239539	782497	1284007	720547	524269	1410499	589507	1475737	892849	1170487	829519	1107157	1279459	20000060
	496477	812527	690673	1309333	1187479	897103	215389	1784617	1102903	1503529	303547	1255963	36787	1963219	744043	868957	13729	1986277	1131049	1696459	20000060
	1588597	1093033	1001467	998539	906973	980593	613813	1386193	1019413	411409	753139	626833	1460497	539509	1373173	881143	1499287	500719	1118863	1246867	20000060
	1477219	1123777	866743	1133263	876229	545473	1306483	693523	1454533	522787	412033	539629	1038823	961183	1460377	1144279	697513	1302493	855727	1587973	20000060
	556939	666979	843553	1156453	1333027	741079	554209	1445797	1258927	1443067	1245037	1267723	99829	1900177	732283	405667	9733	1990273	1594339	754969	20000060
	1488793	1116223	1288249	711757	883783	1732867	1525507	474499	267139	511213	1857679	1565827	1400863	599143	434179	1568923	1793479	206527	431083	142327	20000060
	764059	1125739	1261363	343579	1304089	329587	967363	946249	1697719	1260283	1281349	1329103	475597	997663	1680079	455443	1521043	510613	1153777	595363	20000060
	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 20. It is composed of **equal sums block-bordered prime magic squares** of order 10.

Example 31. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 10. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			20000060	
	1562287	575689	1042597	1496203	1481947	667819	470209	1143013	1150063	410203	207973	780457	449773	801337	1457857	1557769	1114837	344347	1556473	1729207	20000060
	918067	476089	1566883	651943	427447	1230667	671467	1416769	1558759	1081939	1596319	1143697	1533283	641923	620869	394453	1581163	1001563	1083073	403687	20000060
	1643539	1572577	558583	457117	1383493	658219	1354819	1587787	427429	356467	1202437	394249	1940599	1232689	1108363	438847	1013227	266293	1605757	797569	20000060
	499159	859849	1462423	715969	1137883	862123	1284037	537583	1140157	1500847	550843	526213	478243	1090459	1522933	477073	909547	1521763	1473793	1449163	20000060
	1219663	835039	902977	1025623	1174273	825733	974383	1097029	1164967	780343	1493377	1539103	541987	629737	1058353	941653	1370269	1458019	460903	506629	20000060
	1170349	1069459	1507993	1046827	678649	1321357	953179	492013	930547	829657	774853	688783	711163	1320037	1189033	810973	679969	1288843	1311223	1225153	20000060
	568237	1532107	1155823	1211593	1009207	990799	788413	844183	467899	1431769	1463947	1461709	594313	959779	229693	1770313	1040227	1405693	538297	536059	20000060
	735829	1213657	412219	1542889	616513	1341787	645187	1441423	786349	1264177	1294123	1329337	1733713	767317	891643	1561159	986779	59407	670669	705883	20000060
	93097	441247	433123	1348063	1572559	769339	1328539	583237	1523917	1906909	1145359	916933	466723	1358083	1379137	1605553	418843	998443	856309	854647	20000060
	1589803	1424317	957409	503803	518059	1332187	1529797	856993	849943	437719	270799	1219549	1550233	1198669	542149	442237	885169	1655659	443533	1792033	20000060
	1919689	1325659	1558309	919447	882529	1258753	1071943	693529	331579	38593	852757	819187	1454767	1548949	1357549	602983	1175509	750133	341647	1096549	20000060
	1262917	1737199	506263	1124317	300877	1682119	724453	1644667	280129	737089	1621729	1107157	1596697	305563	998983	1632487	969049	862669	527419	378277	20000060
	1627783	527053	296683	1033867	1005079	1429507	457789	1777093	1472953	372223	473419	936919	1905433	345019	502339	1500643	1537897	208687	1063087	1526587	20000060
	402763	1380469	1200643	878167	963913	1036093	1121839	799363	619537	1597243	836749	670333	1407397	1007317	870049	1129957	992689	592609	1329673	1163257	20000060
	828169	778417	1534993	994579	939769	1060237	1005427	465013	1221589	1171837	559123	719143	373393	576379	711973	1288033	1423627	1626613	1280863	1440883	20000060
	581557	357583	1172107	771403	462073	1537933	1228603	827899	1642423	1418449	516757	1167289	502717	1390399	693373	1306633	609607	1497289	832717	1483249	20000060
	370687	497587	1572679	1355863	1634257	365749	644143	427327	1502419	1629319	1417033	1306597	19759	1025917	1724617	275389	974089	1980247	693409	582973	20000060
	1002073	1001839	222913	966139	994927	570499	1542217	1703323	998167	997933	970903	619999	1791319	1654987	1497667	499363	462109	94573	1380007	1029103	20000060
	42979	1719877	1493743	875689	1699129	317887	1275553	355339	262807	1957027	1848103	1472587	403309	1694443	1001023	367519	1030957	1137337	892849	151903	20000060
	1961413	674347	441697	1080559	1117477	741253	928063	1306477	1668427	80317	903457	1180819	545239	451057	642457	1397023	824497	1249873	1658359	1147249	20000060
	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060	20000060

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 20. It is composed of **equal sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 10.

Example 32. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

20	mgc																			10000000
550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	10000000
211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	10000000
253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	10000000
275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	10000000
58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	10000000
330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	10000000
172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	10000000
151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	10000000
304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	10000000
341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	10000000
400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	10000000
125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	10000000
912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	10000000
229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	10000000
984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	10000000
995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	10000000
999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	10000000
999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	10000000
999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	10000000
702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	10000000
10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000	10000000

It is **concentric single-layer bordered** prime magic square of order 20. The internal part of order 18 is the same as given above in the Example 3.20.

3.7 Prime Magic Squares of Order 21

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 21 with different representations.

Example 33. Different Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

21	mgc																				41966673
1777891	1340221	2892811	1932563	2010653	2457383	1294639	1656367	2151943	1863731	2295473	2393189	1392323	2698181	2392067	1557823	2154487	2376139	1717337	1246379	2365073	41966673
3118561	2003641	888721	2658353	2133533	1608713	2558287	1700983	843679	2713589	2184131	1654673	3160601	2160857	1161113	2847799	2029483	1211167	2423999	1776263	1128527	41966673
1114471	2667061	2229391	1809683	2256413	2334503	1250023	1745599	2107327	1975073	2072789	2504531	1929647	1623533	2929391	1682827	1904479	2501143	1187453	2306147	1835189	41966673
1134769	2061187	2844271	1400923	2724229	2563867	1617743	1180733	2767913	2085943	1200499	3162277	1083689	2278301	2316107	1198361	1825163	2251517	1052327	2870717	2346137	41966673
3722911	2013409	303907	3392617	2229673	1066729	3005633	1855463	705293	3225907	2149573	1073239	3125117	1892699	660281	2811503	1758347	705191	3383537	2089727	795917	41966673
1182547	1965631	2892049	1895479	1735117	3058423	943013	2530193	2093183	1136869	3098647	2213203	1469291	1507097	2701709	1265177	1691531	2318333	1833317	1308737	3127127	41966673
1826137	2124601	2782939	1474961	1335641	2808761	1435277	1801781	2679449	1821871	1488343	2524309	1072937	2156897	1925507	1345051	2573071	2362981	1117463	2576669	2732027	41966673
3201361	2244559	1287757	3206921	1873121	539321	3216341	1972169	727997	2647279	1944841	1242403	2571017	1718447	865877	3111631	2093701	1075771	3756617	2142053	527489	41966673
1706179	2364517	2662981	937481	2410601	2271281	1264889	2142557	2509061	1365373	2401339	2067811	1511387	1279997	2363957	1824421	1614331	2842351	1552079	1707437	3166643	41966673
1352209	2813497	2339011	2200943	1787129	2747831	1652359	1793761	2650987	1328279	2312201	1896677	1088917	2510971	1842469	1455197	1322921	2668553	1040813	2402921	2759027	41966673
3155041	2168239	1181437	2792189	2245301	1698413	3030997	2032369	1033741	2414117	1845719	1277321	2567671	1814119	1060567	3028913	1815557	602201	3785801	2067587	349373	41966673
1997467	1522981	2984269	1742771	2703473	2289659	1413751	2270977	2412379	1794761	1379237	2363159	1785769	1117267	2539321	962561	2308193	2175917	1376147	1732253	3094361	41966673
1097699	2341907	2275211	1452977	1895507	2387087	1418239	2403679	2507389	1690811	2010527	2231819	1624279	1407877	2835523	1740421	1507789	2813563	1351403	2121869	2851097	41966673
3082451	1904939	727427	2845967	1911857	977747	3198919	2109769	1020619	2518727	1977719	1436711	3167137	1955893	744649	3093733	2020591	947449	3607817	2108123	608429	41966673
1534667	1467971	2712179	1436627	1928207	2370737	1712149	1815859	2801299	1723619	1944911	2264627	1076263	2503909	2287507	1227619	2533393	2300761	1365149	2094377	2864843	41966673
411937	544723	812761	1340329	1311547	2496271	2747177	2579651	5118713	2898569	2687723	4491761	2110753	3666001	4641037	565427	708221	1045199	301073	635279	852521	41966673
990631	589807	188983	2871991	1716049	560107	5853383	3481847	1110311	4952543	3359351	1766159	6002881	3472597	942313	1252721	772949	293177	1147739	596291	44843	41966673
366853	634891	767677	935827	2120551	2091769	1844981	4384043	4216517	2226941	4030979	3820133	2304157	3279193	4834441	500699	837677	980471	340061	557303	891509	41966673
2175097	2532697	4485097	1111087	2644063	1882921	597659	687083	1224131	336307	498937	747427	529181	1361357	1032299	3018527	2697599	4778663	2720183	3291371	3614987	41966673
5374297	3064297	754297	2651191	1879357	1107523	1462763	836291	209819	938677	527557	116437	1477397	974279	471161	5258399	3498263	1738127	4103651	3208847	2314043	41966673
1643497	3595897	3953497	1875793	1114651	2647627	448451	985499	1074923	307687	556177	718807	916259	587201	1419377	2217863	4298927	3977999	2802707	3126323	3697511	41966673
41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673	41966673

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 21. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3.
 See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc			6010923	3	mgc			6400599	3	mgc			5102949
	1777891	1340221	2892811	6010923		1932563	2010653	2457383	6400599		1294639	1656367	2151943	5102949
	3118561	2003641	888721	6010923		2658353	2133533	1608713	6400599		2558287	1700983	843679	5102949
	1114471	2667061	2229391	6010923		1809683	2256413	2334503	6400599		1250023	1745599	2107327	5102949
	6010923	6010923	6010923	6010923		6400599	6400599	6400599	6400599		5102949	5102949	5102949	5102949
3	mgc			6040227	3	mgc			6689019	3	mgc			5566389
	1134769	2061187	2844271	6040227		1400923	2724229	2563867	6689019		1617743	1180733	2767913	5566389
	3722911	2013409	303907	6040227		3392617	2229673	1066729	6689019		3005633	1855463	705293	5566389
	1182547	1965631	2892049	6040227		1895479	1735117	3058423	6689019		943013	2530193	2093183	5566389
	6040227	6040227	6040227	6040227		6689019	6689019	6689019	6689019		5566389	5566389	5566389	5566389
3	mgc			6733677	3	mgc			5619363	3	mgc			5916507
	1826137	2124601	2782939	6733677		1474961	1335641	2808761	5619363		1435277	1801781	2679449	5916507
	3201361	2244559	1287757	6733677		3206921	1873121	539321	5619363		3216341	1972169	727997	5916507
	1706179	2364517	2662981	6733677		937481	2410601	2271281	5619363		1264889	2142557	2509061	5916507
	6733677	6733677	6733677	6733677		5619363	5619363	5619363	5619363		5916507	5916507	5916507	5916507

Example 34. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

21	mgc																			21000063		
	1579813	52009	1368187	759673	1848193	392143	1707073	507589	785347	1854703	169483	975823	1933123	24049	1042837	1548073	358903	1093033	1675117	122029	1202863	21000063
	788377	1000003	1211629	632473	1000003	1367533	78277	1000003	1921729	121123	1000003	1878883	109717	1000003	1890289	544963	1000003	1455043	527749	1000003	1472257	21000063
	631819	1947997	420193	1607863	151813	1240333	1214659	1492417	292933	1024183	1830523	145303	957169	1975957	66883	906973	1641103	451933	797143	1877977	324889	21000063
	950869	658447	1390693	757243	1549837	692929	995713	450487	1553809	946249	1914007	139753	1079173	652039	1268797	552793	1188619	1258597	886807	1719049	394153	21000063
	1439827	1000003	560179	935689	1000003	1064317	1558099	1000003	441907	193507	1000003	1806499	1189627	1000003	810379	1705807	1000003	294199	507349	1000003	1492657	21000063
	609313	1341559	1049137	1307077	450169	1242763	446197	1549519	1004293	1860253	85999	1053757	731209	1347967	920833	741409	811387	1447213	1605853	280957	1113199	21000063
	602983	1299367	1097659	88897	1869529	1041583	1168639	1382527	448843	429007	1564699	1006303	912463	1225933	861613	864007	1845199	290803	1856059	25087	1118863	21000063
	1494679	1000003	505327	1952689	1000003	47317	280207	1000003	1719799	1577299	1000003	422707	949153	1000003	1050853	426799	1000003	1573207	262807	1000003	1737199	21000063
	902347	700639	1397023	958423	130477	1911109	1551163	617479	831367	993703	435307	1570999	1138393	774073	1087543	1709203	154807	1135999	881143	1974919	143947	21000063
	588619	1020037	1391353	703033	1402309	894667	801469	441877	1756663	928813	440893	1630303	1706533	196837	1096639	1637863	544627	817519	1095433	1361287	543289	21000063
	1802737	1000003	197269	1191637	1000003	808369	1955197	1000003	44809	1701493	1000003	298513	390109	1000003	1609897	179659	1000003	1820347	447859	1000003	1552147	21000063
	608653	979969	1411387	1105339	597697	1296973	243343	1558129	1198537	369703	1559113	1071193	903367	1803169	293473	1182487	1455379	362143	1456717	638719	904573	21000063
	499363	1998943	501703	1478887	65929	1455193	459763	1404919	1135327	971197	301789	1727023	1373683	1117759	508567	788023	1363189	848797	1248979	1339207	411823	21000063
	1002343	1000003	997663	976309	1000003	1023697	1675567	1000003	324439	1755829	1000003	244177	134887	1000003	1865119	1060777	1000003	939229	162847	1000003	1837159	21000063
	1498303	1063	1500643	544813	1934077	521119	864679	595087	1540243	272983	1698217	1028809	1491439	882247	626323	1151209	636817	1211983	1588183	660799	751027	21000063
	1819339	254377	926293	781423	1788229	430357	353833	1471573	1174603	1471123	760477	768409	412333	1230547	1357129	888793	1257247	853969	679207	746869	1573933	21000063
	106957	1000003	1893049	648937	1000003	1351069	1820773	1000003	179233	297289	1000003	1702717	1944799	1000003	55207	965179	1000003	1034827	1894729	1000003	105277	21000063
	1073713	1745629	180667	1569649	211777	1218583	825403	528433	1646173	1231597	1239529	528883	642877	769459	1587673	1146037	742759	1111213	426073	1253137	1320799	21000063
	912103	1340947	746959	1049773	1837477	112759	1110349	738457	1151203	1029859	174877	1795273	1253347	184609	1562053	643129	1117867	1239013	1906909	80527	1012573	21000063
	834859	1000003	1165147	62989	1000003	1937017	1040857	1000003	959149	1765417	1000003	234589	1308709	1000003	691297	1595887	1000003	404119	105667	1000003	1894339	21000063
	1253047	659059	1087903	1887247	162529	950233	848803	1261549	889657	204733	1825129	970147	437953	1815397	746659	760993	882139	1356877	987433	1919479	93097	21000063
21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 21. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 4. See below few examples of order 3:

3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	1854703	169483	975823	3000009		1548073	358903	1093033	3000009
	121123	1000003	1878883	3000009		544963	1000003	1455043	3000009
	1024183	1830523	145303	3000009		906973	1641103	451933	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	864007	1845199	290803	3000009		788023	1363189	848797	3000009
	426799	1000003	1573207	3000009		1060777	1000003	939229	3000009
	1709203	154807	1135999	3000009		1151209	636817	1211983	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009
3	mgc			3000009	3	mgc			3000009
	412333	1230547	1357129	3000009		1906909	80527	1012573	3000009
	1944799	1000003	55207	3000009		105667	1000003	1894339	3000009
	642877	769459	1587673	3000009		987433	1919479	93097	3000009
	3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009		3000009	3000009	3000009	3000009

Example 35. Different Sums Blocks of Order 7. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

21	mgc																			197419467	
9469777	9494077	9494767	9496687	9497647	9498067	9494917	8978377	9033967	9036997	9037477	9037687	9037867	9035707	9647767	9685267	9687697	9687787	9689377	9691147	9686407	197419467
9493417	9455497	9493117	9493357	9527017	9492397	9491137	9032197	9000907	9032017	9032167	9046897	9029497	9024397	9684967	9656167	9684607	9685057	9702877	9682327	9679447	197419467
9493507	9493087	9492697	9485737	9498397	9491467	9491047	9032857	9029707	9031927	9013327	9039637	9026887	9023737	9687367	9683137	9685387	9669997	9691237	9681277	9677047	197419467
9496177	9505087	9497977	9492277	9486577	9479467	9488377	9040417	9038467	9036007	9028297	9020587	9018127	9016177	9690097	9693037	9688057	9682207	9676357	9671377	9674317	197419467
9498547	9515557	9486157	9498817	9491857	9468997	9486007	9041377	9045307	9016957	9043267	9024667	9011287	9015217	9692047	9696607	9673177	9694417	9679027	9667807	9672367	197419467
9504877	9492157	9491437	9491197	9457537	9529057	9479677	9051967	9027097	9024577	9024427	9009697	9055687	9004627	9695197	9682087	9679807	9679357	9661537	9708247	9669217	197419467
9489637	9490477	9489787	9487867	9486907	9486487	9514777	9020887	9022627	9019597	9019117	9018907	9018727	9078217	9678007	9679147	9676717	9676627	9675037	9673267	9716647	197419467
9546007	9595147	9595237	9598597	9598807	9599467	9602737	9356317	9403327	9403357	9407407	9407767	9412717	9415597	9172087	9215497	9217237	9217657	9218557	9220117	9215827	197419467
9593677	9559597	9592567	9593407	9617617	9591097	9588037	9403237	9387607	9401467	9401767	9412687	9401107	9398617	9215317	9187957	9214687	9215047	9224947	9212347	9206677	197419467
9596317	9591157	9596557	9572137	9603877	9590557	9585397	9407317	9401377	9404737	9382207	9415837	9400477	9394537	9218047	9212887	9211957	9207097	9213937	9209107	9203947	197419467
9601057	9602407	9598177	9590857	9583537	9579307	9580657	9411877	9405547	9412027	9400927	9389827	9396307	9389977	9219247	9219277	9212977	9210997	9209017	9202717	9202747	197419467
9609247	9610507	9577837	9609577	9585157	9571207	9572467	9420487	9409357	9386017	9419647	9397117	9392497	9381367	9219907	9225217	9208057	9214897	9210037	9196777	9202087	197419467
9610717	9590617	9589147	9588307	9564097	9622117	9570997	9420997	9400747	9400387	9400087	9389167	9414247	9380857	9226207	9209647	9207307	9206947	9197047	9234037	9195787	197419467
9578977	9586567	9586477	9583117	9582907	9582247	9635707	9386257	9398527	9398497	9394447	9394087	9389137	9445537	9206167	9206497	9204757	9204337	9203437	9201877	9249907	197419467
9077857	9124057	9124777	9126787	9127537	9129607	9126907	9721927	9778297	9782137	9782917	9783187	9786277	9780157	9253207	9312547	9315247	9316687	9318157	9326287	9324907	197419467
9123787	9088297	9122257	9124117	9143437	9120127	9115507	9777577	9759247	9776167	9776257	9781747	9774367	9769537	9312067	9279367	9310597	9310927	9336697	9310297	9307087	197419467
9124327	9120367	9127777	9102547	9128617	9118927	9114967	9780367	9774397	9773767	9761617	9785287	9772717	9766747	9321517	9310507	9315637	9295327	9317767	9308647	9297637	197419467
9127627	9128827	9120487	9119647	9118807	9110467	9111667	9783667	9776407	9785077	9773557	9762037	9770707	9763447	9323617	9321937	9311707	9309577	9307447	9297217	9295537	197419467
9132577	9141577	9110677	9136747	9111517	9097717	9106717	9789937	9784987	9761827	9785497	9773347	9762127	9757177	9324247	9327217	9301387	9323827	9303517	9291937	9294907	197419467
9138967	9119167	9117037	9115177	9095857	9150997	9100327	9794467	9772747	9770947	9770857	9765367	9787867	9752647	9338137	9308857	9308557	9308227	9282457	9339787	9281017	197419467
9112387	9115237	9114517	9112507	9111757	9109687	9161437	9766957	9768817	9764977	9764197	9763927	9760837	9825187	9294247	9306607	9303907	9302467	9300997	9292867	9365947	197419467
197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467	197419467

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 21. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 7.
 See below few examples of order 7:

3	mgc				28476831								3	mgc																			29320671		
		9492697	9485737	9498397	28476831										9773767	9761617	9785287	29320671															29320671		
		9497977	9492277	9486577	28476831										9785077	9773557	9762037	29320671															29320671		
		9486157	9498817	9491857	28476831										9761827	9785497	9773347	29320671															29320671		
		28476831	28476831	28476831	28476831										29320671	29320671	29320671	29320671																29320671	
5	mgc														5	mgc																		48867785	
		9455497	9493117	9493357	9527017	9492397	47461385										9759247	9776167	9776257	9781747	9774367	48867785												48867785	
		9493087	9492697	9485737	9498397	9491467	47461385										9774397	9773767	9761617	9785287	9772717	48867785												48867785	
		9505087	9497977	9492277	9486577	9479467	47461385										9776407	9785077	9773557	9762037	9770707	48867785												48867785	
		9515557	9486157	9498817	9491857	9468997	47461385										9784987	9761827	9785497	9773347	9762127	48867785												48867785	
		9492157	9491437	9491197	9457537	9529057	47461385										9772747	9770947	9770857	9765367	9787867	48867785												48867785	
		47461385	47461385	47461385	47461385	47461385	47461385										48867785	48867785	48867785	48867785	48867785	48867785	48867785											48867785	
7	mgc														7	mgc																			68414899
		9469777	9494077	9494767	9496687	9497647	9498067	9494917	66445939								9721927	9778297	9782137	9782917	9783187	9786277	9780157	68414899										68414899	
		9493417	9455497	9493117	9493357	9527017	9492397	9491137	66445939								9777577	9759247	9776167	9776257	9781747	9774367	9769537	68414899										68414899	
		9493507	9493087	9492697	9485737	9498397	9491467	9491047	66445939								9780367	9774397	9773767	9761617	9785287	9772717	9766747	68414899										68414899	
		9496177	9505087	9497977	9492277	9486577	9479467	9488377	66445939								9783667	9776407	9785077	9773557	9762037	9770707	9763447	68414899										68414899	
		9498547	9515557	9486157	9498817	9491857	9468997	9486007	66445939								9789937	9784987	9761827	9785497	9773347	9762127	9757177	68414899										68414899	
		9504877	9492157	9491437	9491197	9457537	9529057	9479677	66445939								9794467	9772747	9770947	9770857	9765367	9787867	9752647	68414899										68414899	
		9489637	9490477	9489787	9487867	9486907	9486487	9514777	66445939								9766957	9768817	9764977	9764197	9763927	9760837	9825187	68414899										68414899	
		66445939	66445939	66445939	66445939	66445939	66445939	66445939	66445939								68414899	68414899	68414899	68414899	68414899	68414899	68414899	68414899										68414899	

Example 36. *Equal Sums Blocks of Order 7.* Let's consider a following prime magic square:

21	mgc																			21000063	
1603297	891643	500029	868123	753793	430699	1952437	1721593	854263	393997	552397	601747	884077	1991947	1585897	903607	958333	486433	769039	824833	1471879	21000063
1383367	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	616639	1548073	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	451933	1044739	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	955267	21000063
267229	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1732777	968959	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	1031047	1375243	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	624763	21000063
1672453	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	327553	1125283	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	874723	1235419	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	764587	21000063
358417	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1641589	798067	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	1201939	932839	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	1067167	21000063
1667689	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	332317	829987	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	1170019	297757	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	1702249	21000063
47569	1108363	1499977	1131883	1246213	1569307	396709	8059	1145743	1606009	1447609	1398259	1115929	278413	528127	1096399	1041673	1513573	1230967	1175173	414109	21000063
1424749	868453	683863	631753	525157	974749	1891297	1708669	576967	919183	721219	622159	455527	1996297	1704343	868873	859849	770233	493573	670333	1632817	21000063
1647949	1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	352057	895813	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1104193	939997	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	1060009	21000063
310663	1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	1689343	1064179	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	935827	1341883	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	658123	21000063
754969	566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1245037	1544449	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	455557	527407	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	1472599	21000063
1498969	1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	501037	325219	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1674787	1073239	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	926767	21000063
1254013	214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	745993	1457983	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	542023	1045963	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	954043	21000063
108709	1131553	1316143	1368253	1474849	1025257	575257	3709	1423039	1080823	1278787	1377847	1544479	291337	367189	1131133	1140157	1229773	1506433	1329673	295663	21000063
1714957	970903	858883	761347	307669	526069	1860193	1655209	945367	373063	875923	874879	366397	1909183	1614409	814309	525979	924499	422557	830419	1867849	21000063
1329709	1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	670297	747427	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1252579	1123093	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	876913	21000063
1629109	851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	370897	1555717	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	444289	304933	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	1695073	21000063
389083	1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1610923	436687	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	1563319	1560883	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	439123	21000063
989827	789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1010179	1535539	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	464467	1064593	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	935413	21000063
807523	18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	1192483	978619	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	1021387	1199953	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	800053	21000063
139813	1029103	1141123	1238659	1692337	1473937	285049	90823	1054639	1626943	1124083	1125127	1633609	344797	132157	1185697	1474027	1075507	1577449	1169587	385597	21000063
21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 21. It is composed of **equal sums prime magic squares** of order 7. See below few examples of order 7:

21	mgc																			21000063	
1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	21000063
69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	21000063
308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	21000063
265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	21000063
511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	21000063
385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	21000063
325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	21000063
363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	21000063
293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	21000063
399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	21000063
593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	21000063
580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	21000063
610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	21000063
1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	21000063
1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	21000063
1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	21000063
1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	21000063
1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	21000063
1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	21000063
1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	21000063
1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	21000063
21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063	21000063

It is **concentric single-layer bordered** prime magic square of order 21. The internal part of order 19 is the same as given above in the Example 3.25.

3.8 Prime Magic Squares of Order 22

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 22 with different representations.

Example 38. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																				46200066	
399719	240913	1057739	1527703	397723	1492417	941617	1292659	565567	2086127	416693	683693	1904087	501383	3904973	4157749	4192759	4199813	4199963	4198729	4199633	3638407	46200066
398407	2192093	1704559	1673393	1903103	2500417	1422857	1625831	2368187	1623907	2638931	2283403	2103163	2157821	2574977	3042367	2778023	1945969	2163107	1412219	1885733	3801599	46200066
2092403	2163281	1531253	2057431	1721183	2297747	1867211	1898107	1854227	2397007	2311417	2150671	1790309	2817887	2951731	2604521	2179049	1665137	2154533	2076967	1510391	2107603	46200066
105407	1667833	2062673	1821791	1920851	1492661	2024531	2127443	2272657	2321959	2089039	2098277	2140129	2087993	1681157	3315779	3468259	2274653	1923059	1252469	1956847	4094599	46200066
1231669	1449941	2174663	1920533	1928011	1626467	2602693	2265911	1422221	2306531	1610017	2117053	2615803	3489487	3345323	1590521	2127857	1521269	1166329	2665373	2054057	2968337	46200066
145253	1554227	1776433	2153699	2302757	2143969	1499011	1579321	2346191	2572133	2334557	2190329	1961857	2941223	2287421	2083009	3223799	2085929	1546453	1538441	1879301	4054753	46200066
1998473	1400417	2349209	2323121	1714369	1884907	1469081	2115853	2098651	2228333	2179609	2360363	2290571	2901989	2378443	3215231	2039789	1360349	2217143	2018573	1454059	2201533	46200066
1981099	2404931	733697	2381089	2267399	1641077	1207909	2775649	1943857	2777311	3255557	1263347	1762661	2796707	2200889	2740889	2796967	1709243	1257647	1556761	2526473	2218907	46200066
1820747	2427541	2927777	929207	1502591	1898539	3392491	1097669	1179793	1481099	1289153	3244837	3043787	1895533	3668699	2496323	2474897	1894603	2028881	1936349	1190291	2379259	46200066
1246943	2755421	2544797	2456243	2851111	1976687	1909109	2759069	2763931	1187629	1836287	1499123	2274149	2236823	1387069	2038969	1285351	1874857	2412439	1516609	2434387	2953063	46200066
529127	2527961	2828641	2296433	2954537	2110321	2503559	2812967	1981949	1740731	2096867	1294561	1665029	1794769	2007301	1301171	1844971	1705273	2293273	1884409	2355337	3670879	46200066
1316239	2805703	2941541	2540957	2319371	2103389	613499	3478771	3213137	2104607	1464257	1941503	1286821	1642939	3088009	551731	1665533	1488343	749677	3310933	2689339	2883767	46200066
972637	2518487	2292593	3313939	2482553	3218399	4382629	357989	1449779	1764221	1399777	2062001	1571189	1273681	465833	3056341	2152357	3169819	2782903	1526341	759229	3227369	46200066
4112497	1802621	1232171	1868371	1624913	2373989	1884293	1330943	2067019	1883627	2815171	2885261	2287409	2089567	2453027	2347313	2510537	2419181	1687381	2385499	2051767	87509	46200066
2303359	1038253	1494347	2033573	1961903	2410519	1376723	1961549	1907453	2158061	3044651	1888063	2780693	2642537	2225057	2370103	2162747	2089093	1565911	2486623	2402201	1896647	46200066
4171619	1306979	489367	2510789	2220941	1709189	2465129	1852843	1629083	2648911	2515127	2423627	2283803	2707349	2558813	2246471	1887811	2596873	2566757	1924537	1455661	28387	46200066
4065953	2380223	3312191	115343	720319	1162547	1930099	2510909	2052689	3180869	1496519	2674517	2519563	1960991	2163547	2436557	2839349	1438681	2723779	1747169	2634199	134053	46200066
4185683	2942749	1974851	2170291	2516257	2395307	2253193	2278343	2522393	1530839	1934117	1730437	2427731	1368803	1059017	1058027	1076917	2642201	2231609	2894929	2992049	14323	46200066
4175827	1859281	2971537	2125567	2647763	2143733	2597897	2288807	2418799	1642049	2253289	2143019	1584767	901907	968917	979787	1712153	2511011	2545237	2652011	3052529	24179	46200066
4191947	2130367	2290573	2216471	2966737	1808843	1536683	3025849	3077861	1740359	342497	2884319	2655949	1275457	1489463	1124597	673247	2210837	1719989	3843551	2986411	8059	46200066
4193459	2671751	2367187	3091819	1473391	3101353	3061463	1856237	1430183	2709877	3093221	865349	954677	1016597	1045367	1400353	1100447	3396739	4263953	1370297	1729799	6547	46200066
561599	3959093	3142267	2672303	3802283	2707589	3258389	2907347	3634439	2113879	3783313	3516313	2295919	3698623	295033	42257	7247	193	43	1277	373	3800287	46200066
46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066	46200066

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 22 embedded with a prime magic square of order 20 with **different sums** prime magic squares of order 4. The prime magic square of order 20 is the same as given in Example 3.26.

Example 39. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																				22000066	
1190737	1105759	1762333	1936057	331063	579967	645937	161137	1104919	1017319	1923253	1745593	149119	771703	1650157	222913	1434457	178597	1182487	1488559	1209163	208837	22000066
797977	1448989	621337	1378669	551017	1101253	889879	1110127	898753	1164967	918193	1081813	835039	1172467	922333	1077673	827539	1177843	866953	1133053	822163	1202029	22000066
164239	603817	1823149	176857	1396189	907723	1746127	253879	1092283	849019	1682413	317593	1150987	862669	1674913	325093	1137337	881233	1669537	330469	1118773	1835767	22000066
1376203	129127	1454059	545947	1870879	281539	1137883	862123	1718467	308359	1169713	830293	1691647	291349	1173853	826153	1708657	272179	1178623	821383	1727827	623803	22000066
1803169	1818079	101467	1898539	181927	1709497	226123	1773883	290509	1677667	229693	1770313	322339	1673527	228913	1771093	326479	1668757	284899	1715107	331249	196837	22000066
1285267	1752397	251359	1748647	247609	1781173	258109	1741897	218833	1638913	329347	1670659	361093	1678639	354877	1645129	321367	1682389	355513	1644493	317617	714739	22000066
725449	307423	1877353	122653	1692583	283303	1848577	151429	1716703	401053	1903339	96667	1598953	331777	1863613	136393	1668229	370537	1859863	140143	1629469	1274557	22000066
108967	80629	1770187	229819	1919377	90403	1784617	215389	1909603	94327	1676533	323473	1905679	126037	1678693	321313	1873969	89137	1684303	315703	1910869	1891039	22000066
145633	1859563	101113	1898893	140443	1845133	108709	1891297	154873	1865719	90793	1909213	134287	1863559	102829	1897177	136447	1857949	100333	1899673	142057	1854373	22000066
1773979	1782289	235273	1764733	217717	1788433	209857	1790149	211573	1325557	661099	1338907	674449	1364617	666889	1333117	635389	1387417	652369	1347637	612589	226027	22000066
149953	258127	1866973	133033	1741879	243829	1860829	139177	1756177	692239	1873507	126499	1307767	648259	1834447	165559	1351747	665719	1811647	188359	1334287	1850053	22000066
534049	93553	1783219	216787	1906453	108517	1790029	209977	1891489	122209	1339057	660949	1877797	155689	1367617	632389	1844317	136399	1388587	611419	1863607	1465957	22000066
892093	1866043	114547	1885459	133963	1859233	139297	1860709	140773	1860007	126349	1873657	139999	1831447	131059	1868947	168559	1810477	147409	1852597	189529	1107913	22000066
1331059	1175569	836863	1163143	824437	1200349	861823	1138183	799657	1219843	857407	1142599	780163	1674997	288913	1711093	325009	1732267	260419	1739587	267739	668947	22000066
354643	867487	1805653	194353	1132519	878833	1780873	219133	1121173	868957	1761379	238627	1131049	295129	1887433	112573	1704877	322549	1830163	169843	1677457	1645363	22000066
343333	163573	1187839	812167	1836433	150247	1210639	789367	1849759	176629	1246639	753367	1823377	181219	1713763	286243	1818787	126493	1743727	256279	1873513	1656673	22000066
1918549	1793383	169657	1830349	206623	1770583	146677	1853329	229423	1734583	134587	1865419	265423	1848667	109903	1890103	151339	1818703	165703	1834303	181303	81457	22000066
1952989	1742989	299287	1700719	257017	1522483	474583	1525423	477523	1528237	461017	1538989	471769	1540879	493573	1506433	459127	1546759	457813	1542193	453247	47017	22000066
1830757	301867	1820509	179497	1698139	472057	1868983	131023	1527949	475669	1863229	136777	1524337	471217	1850587	149419	1528789	460063	1844707	155299	1539943	169249	22000066
349303	152077	1760419	239587	1847929	137413	1523407	476599	1862593	140983	1536343	463663	1859023	137659	1541209	458797	1862347	149503	1547779	452227	1850503	1650703	22000066
1180549	1803079	119797	1880209	196927	1868059	133039	1866967	131947	1855123	139423	1860583	144883	1850257	114643	1885363	149749	1843687	149713	1850293	156319	819457	22000066
1791169	894247	237673	63949	1668943	1420039	1354069	1838869	895087	982687	76753	254413	1850887	1228303	349849	1777093	565549	1821409	817519	511447	790843	809269	22000066
22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 22 embedded with a prime magic square of order 20 with **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 4. The prime magic square of order 20 is the same as given in Example 3.27.

Example 40. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																				22000066	
1790263	1636039	1085767	325939	1090963	674449	525457	551269	1510273	664687	1407247	1530703	944893	1672339	950497	1351117	418843	387007	448993	1578553	1197829	256939	22000066
1125193	929323	861937	1377967	1497019	1245169	315361	385279	767527	735157	1071121	1194163	460087	1597873	1614391	1859071	225769	959083	848203	522757	1532803	874813	22000066
956107	1846849	756703	1105537	1684609	517717	864439	554467	225931	1184269	445339	2257117	1461667	667141	1906543	433117	1380517	502429	631717	1319023	254929	1043899	22000066
1592659	1400353	2110189	1182283	254377	964213	591391	1284691	654889	25087	718387	1328491	1789993	1345117	900241	1361743	1121203	1634317	817723	1129	514243	407347	22000066
399613	615493	679957	1259029	1607863	1749073	1264597	125509	1083847	755311	45181	1114651	783691	2023093	1228567	1575583	1258483	316423	1003729	1133017	376963	1600393	22000066
1165147	1119397	1502629	986599	867547	1435243	238657	924499	542251	574621	994417	831163	2230147	1092361	1075843	1496071	102643	676363	787243	1112689	1409677	834859	22000066
459463	1280113	922717	951151	695257	665947	1349287	720289	913279	442753	120157	1314127	809587	1581037	1475827	1273687	983119	1239319	1570879	613141	1078387	1540543	22000066
950479	287611	741337	533821	1433953	1518463	380803	753847	431449	942163	1037503	1880947	1601107	722539	1548913	700759	1529761	936379	334021	2020507	664177	1049527	22000066
523207	1457503	1595653	903037	210421	348571	283519	897469	709153	520837	1134787	1402153	1238659	1290853	1343047	1179553	1341187	2181097	1096969	12841	852751	1476799	22000066
1005349	349831	372121	1272253	1064737	1456243	234007	476143	986857	664459	1184299	549019	1032793	1859167	980599	2032687	515227	173431	1859917	1257559	1678711	994657	22000066
387397	1140127	883357	854923	1110817	525961	1298149	698017	505027	975553	69019	1308019	1772119	1000669	1105879	1267579	1115551	954619	623059	1580797	1210819	1612609	22000066
1291063	1125343	1096189	1114159	483757	1347667	1000507	1222561	1340653	589207	897907	247309	366907	1304599	1217809	1812571	421639	1118629	370009	1450249	1472389	708943	22000066
790033	1100857	1702177	710089	688003	965989	583537	1051957	745981	1232563	1436797	1123219	1608379	598219	762919	856459	1538917	970969	404167	1524613	394249	1209973	22000066
775603	1731397	19249	1033423	2047597	335449	1208833	1190773	1010167	829561	811501	1655089	144379	989839	1835299	324589	531919	1520227	966583	412939	1401247	1224403	22000066
488779	490339	1378843	1356757	364669	1576507	1135531	787771	1274353	968377	884803	1756471	1216759	1381459	371299	223207	1879663	408553	1528999	962197	53503	1511227	22000066
923449	719179	970657	952687	1583089	941503	1122427	797773	679681	1431127	1019827	167107	1612771	675079	761869	1732369	460777	814537	1563157	482917	1511527	1076557	22000066
578533	666727	318247	1147387	1400107	873877	1491157	2069449	2015347	501829	2051233	407713	388897	473497	124309	476599	1044367	386161	1216807	1471117	1475233	1421473	22000066
1289557	507919	1090519	444289	1108999	1254619	2131099	1212649	1555507	2109253	1120507	217429	261223	284857	576529	530977	1431733	1868527	355723	1131961	805741	710449	22000066
1097869	1019839	899749	881269	862789	742699	2421253	2522407	1625803	729199	830353	291997	689509	374203	58897	456409	1194343	382171	1118737	1855303	1043131	902137	22000066
1081243	1323199	653539	1318249	672019	439339	885133	1142353	1696099	2038957	2366473	682069	171877	463549	487183	66337	1161001	1105513	1881751	368947	1076473	918763	22000066
1585993	888661	1444291	615151	362431	1095811	1200373	1182157	1236259	2749777	1760449	271807	359509	274909	624097	340693	762241	1851313	1020667	766357	1193107	414013	22000066
1743067	363967	914239	1674067	909043	1325557	1474549	1448737	489733	1335319	592759	469303	1055113	327667	1049509	648889	1581163	1612999	1551013	421453	802177	209743	22000066
22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 22 embedded with a prime magic square of order 20 with **different sums** prime magic squares of order 4. The prime magic square of order 20 is the same as given in Example 3.28.

Example 41. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 5. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																				22000066	
393697	22027	1720123	955477	814537	1197649	1639153	1600603	213253	889873	1747969	123289	1638913	1212649	645703	617479	230143	1396327	1456123	1088089	453247	1943743	22000066
72649	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	1401217	929323	509449	605497	1554529	1927357	22000066
1562263	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	1293967	1059433	805249	1135327	706039	437743	22000066
1706539	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	1640467	1075897	1000003	924109	359539	293467	22000066
611263	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	218887	864679	1194757	940573	1781119	1388743	22000066
785347	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	445477	1070683	1490557	1394509	598789	1214659	22000066
1472587	1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	1687297	727939	447883	345979	1790917	527419	22000066
563743	1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	848923	963667	390499	1645843	1151083	1436263	22000066
266293	566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	310627	1682179	1000003	317827	1689379	1733713	22000066
1522933	1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	1944079	354163	1609507	1036339	55927	477073	22000066
1803457	214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	209089	1272067	1552123	1654027	312709	196549	22000066
72547	1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	1187749	495973	828169	620647	1867477	1927459	22000066
683083	851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	511867	852289	941167	1206553	1488139	1316923	22000066
1827937	1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	1562593	1354267	1000003	645739	437413	172069	22000066
1814413	789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	1605277	793453	1058839	1147717	394729	185593	22000066
1387417	18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	132529	1504033	1171837	1379359	812257	612589	22000066
1276903	1613707	263737	549517	945787	1627267	1010263	577807	833719	720547	1857679	1597243	511963	253879	644383	1992547	1519657	349579	938857	433369	1758553	723103	22000066
756289	1066063	750943	523207	1725859	933943	659299	729367	966139	1304503	1340707	1495867	1635583	697693	666733	504139	758929	1459099	250057	1290853	1241077	1243717	22000066
247363	1370227	1974919	1000003	25087	629779	1302919	1575139	1000003	424867	697087	1450453	31153	1000003	1968853	549553	1422973	831757	1000003	1168249	577033	1752643	22000066
1264027	577279	274147	1476799	1249063	1422727	1885207	695503	1033867	1270639	114799	448993	1333273	1302313	364423	1551013	1057003	709153	1749949	540907	943003	735979	22000066
1853053	372739	1736269	1450489	1054219	386299	142327	1422199	1166287	1279459	989743	7459	1488043	1746127	1355623	402763	241453	1650427	1061149	1566637	480349	146953	22000066
56263	1977979	279883	1044529	1185469	802357	360853	399403	1786753	1110133	252037	1876717	361093	787357	1354303	1382527	1769863	603679	543883	911917	1546759	1606309	22000066
22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 22 embedded with a prime magic square of order 20 with **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 5. The prime magic square of order 20 is the same as given in Example 3.29.

Example 42. Block-Bordered Nested with Four Equal Sums Blocks of Order 10. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																				22000066	
805633	1492417	1051153	976777	1193947	1687963	1422523	415567	679969	479497	861613	327889	912979	1122397	1185697	1164607	819499	1596013	302053	1674787	624847	1202239	22000066
699529	1576747	1063747	657439	335953	733963	1624963	569053	1626613	1299979	511573	181927	1244197	1145077	1483507	950149	787519	482689	998443	934033	1792489	1300477	22000066
1403167	1009207	1348987	1041949	958057	651019	796339	1065109	934897	1203667	990799	1596139	1098439	513319	1486687	901567	804337	560179	1439827	1195669	403867	596839	22000066
1647769	1362637	1007557	567829	1432177	992449	1324117	672703	1327303	675889	637369	1652719	1308607	1124083	875923	691399	556849	1156699	843307	1443157	347287	352237	22000066
1588879	458377	667819	941167	1058839	1332187	817087	406573	1593433	1182919	1541629	1225879	968197	1597753	402253	1031809	1534207	856417	1143589	465799	774127	411127	22000066
543289	493393	975649	1449067	550939	1024357	1062469	1855627	144379	937537	1506613	1192579	624769	764857	1235149	1375237	1104619	1426717	573289	895387	807427	1456717	22000066
1028107	1072363	987013	1164343	835663	1012993	1110643	1007089	992917	889363	927643	1461697	1543999	437953	1562053	456007	498643	443419	1556587	1501363	538309	971899	22000066
684829	613969	441703	731593	1268413	1558303	622849	1555717	444289	1377157	1386037	590797	966817	697267	1302739	1033189	965047	1573933	426073	1034959	1409209	1315177	22000066
323083	353527	1226977	374287	1625719	773029	727123	1126963	873043	1272883	1646479	1178557	1060519	1812589	187417	939487	1247479	783733	1216273	752527	821449	1676923	22000066
1322227	1571377	1344319	1729789	270217	655687	1539397	310243	1689763	460609	428629	712219	428677	1052203	947803	1571329	1288843	1198927	801079	711163	1287787	677779	22000066
1234333	1488433	936259	1342567	1664053	1266043	375043	1430953	373393	700027	423259	207517	755809	854929	516499	1049857	1212487	1517317	1001563	1065973	1818079	765673	22000066
562579	739723	874267	738643	1656427	695917	1670419	1032643	1053757	302287	1235947	1404643	670903	1524409	1002343	319927	1544563	478963	1489393	846229	718657	1437427	22000066
798517	475897	1416799	1490353	509653	583207	1189897	556483	1443523	810109	1524109	1294597	1470613	1356877	643129	529393	775267	1551619	448387	1224739	705409	1201489	22000066
468709	1696327	909247	607357	1392649	1090759	695503	1467673	532333	1304503	303679	727459	749167	1195849	804157	1250839	1462939	1264177	735829	537067	1272547	1531297	22000066
1554349	715999	861439	1211629	788377	1138567	1217509	1760467	239539	782497	1284007	720547	524269	1410499	589507	1475737	892849	1170487	829519	1107157	1279459	445657	22000066
505657	496477	812527	690673	1309333	1187479	897103	215389	1784617	1102903	1503529	303547	1255963	36787	1963219	744043	868957	13729	1986277	1131049	1696459	1494349	22000066
1624453	1588597	1093033	1001467	998539	906973	980593	613813	1386193	1019413	411409	753139	626833	1460497	539509	1373173	881143	1499287	500719	1118863	1246867	375553	22000066
1029859	1477219	1123777	866743	1133263	876229	545473	1306483	693523	1454533	522787	412033	539629	1038823	961183	1460377	1144279	697513	1302493	855727	1587973	970147	22000066
1650157	556939	666979	843553	1156453	1333027	741079	554209	1445797	1258927	1443067	1245037	1267723	99829	1900177	732283	405667	9733	1990273	1594339	754969	349849	22000066
1661557	1488793	1116223	1288249	711757	883783	1732867	1525507	474499	267139	511213	1857679	1565827	1400863	599143	434179	1568923	1793479	206527	431083	142327	338449	22000066
65617	764059	1125739	1261363	343579	1304089	329587	967363	946249	1697719	1260283	1281349	1329103	475597	997663	1680079	455443	1521043	510613	1153777	595363	1934389	22000066
797767	507589	948853	1023229	806059	312043	577483	1584439	1320037	1520509	1138393	1672117	1087027	877609	814309	835399	1180507	403993	1697953	325219	1375159	1194373	22000066
22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 22 embedded with a prime magic square of order 20 with four **equal sums block-bordered** prime magic squares of order 10. These are again composed of four equal sums prime magic squares of order 4. The prime magic square of order 20 is the same as given in Example 3.42.

Example 43. Block-Bordered Nested with Four Equal Sums Concentric Blocks of Order 10. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																			22000066		
1141123	1369657	1021663	788353	387397	1578883	783019	1047883	1013569	410629	301993	1635307	1642723	1323199	1601659	1239457	1072363	1024663	485593	691759	568627	870547	22000066
1095343	1562287	575689	1042597	1496203	1481947	667819	470209	1143013	1150063	410203	207973	780457	449773	801337	1457857	1557769	1114837	344347	1556473	1729207	904663	22000066
434803	918067	476089	1566883	651943	427447	1230667	671467	1416769	1558759	1081939	1596319	1143697	1533283	641923	620869	394453	1581163	1001563	1083073	403687	1565203	22000066
632473	1643539	1572577	558583	457117	1383493	658219	1354819	1587787	427429	356467	1202437	394249	1940599	1232689	1108363	438847	1013227	266293	1605757	797569	1367533	22000066
1605907	499159	859849	1462423	715969	1137883	862123	1284037	537583	1140157	1500847	550843	526213	478243	1090459	1522933	477073	909547	1521763	1473793	1449163	394099	22000066
1413439	1219663	835039	902977	1025623	1174273	825733	974383	1097029	1164967	780343	1493377	1539103	541987	629737	1058353	941653	1370269	1458019	460903	506629	586567	22000066
322669	1170349	1069459	1507993	1046827	678649	1321357	953179	492013	930547	829657	774853	688783	711163	1320037	1189033	810973	679969	1288843	1311223	1225153	1677337	22000066
833293	568237	1532107	1155823	1211593	1009207	990799	788413	844183	467899	1431769	1463947	1461709	594313	959779	229693	1770313	1040227	1405693	538297	536059	1166713	22000066
560683	735829	1213657	412219	1542889	616513	1341787	645187	1441423	786349	1264177	1294123	1329337	1733713	767317	891643	1561159	986779	59407	670669	705883	1439323	22000066
1431307	93097	441247	433123	1348063	1572559	769339	1328539	583237	1523917	1906909	1145359	916933	466723	1358083	1379137	1605553	418843	998443	856309	854647	568699	22000066
1473919	1589803	1424317	957409	503803	518059	1332187	1529797	856993	849943	437719	270799	1219549	1550233	1198669	542149	442237	885169	1655659	443533	1792033	526087	22000066
849427	1919689	1325659	1558309	919447	882529	1258753	1071943	693529	331579	38593	852757	819187	1454767	1548949	1357549	602983	1175509	750133	341647	1096549	1150579	22000066
817933	1262917	1737199	506263	1124317	300877	1682119	724453	1644667	280129	737089	1621729	1107157	1596697	305563	998983	1632487	969049	862669	527419	378277	1182073	22000066
1167277	1627783	527053	296683	1033867	1005079	1429507	457789	1777093	1472953	372223	473419	936919	1905433	345019	502339	1500643	1537897	208687	1063087	1526587	832729	22000066
410317	402763	1380469	1200643	878167	963913	1036093	1121839	799363	619537	1597243	836749	670333	1407397	1007317	870049	1129957	992689	592609	1329673	1163257	1589689	22000066
930409	828169	778417	1534993	994579	939769	1060237	1005427	465013	1221589	1171837	559123	719143	373393	576379	711973	1288033	1423627	1626613	1280863	1440883	1069597	22000066
1531093	581557	357583	1172107	771403	462073	1537933	1228603	827899	1642423	1418449	516757	1167289	502717	1390399	693373	1306633	609607	1497289	832717	1483249	468913	22000066
902137	370687	497587	1572679	1355863	1634257	365749	644143	427327	1502419	1629319	1417033	1306597	19759	1025917	1724617	275389	974089	1980247	693409	582973	1097869	22000066
415039	1002073	1001839	222913	966139	994927	570499	1542217	1703323	998167	997933	970903	619999	1791319	1654987	1497667	499363	462109	94573	1380007	1029103	1584967	22000066
1610017	42979	1719877	1493743	875689	1699129	317887	1275553	355339	262807	1957027	1848103	1472587	403309	1694443	1001023	367519	1030957	1137337	892849	151903	389989	22000066
1291999	1961413	674347	441697	1080559	1117477	741253	928063	1306477	1668427	80317	903457	1180819	545239	451057	642457	1397023	824497	1249873	1658359	1147249	708007	22000066
1129459	630349	978343	1211653	1612609	421123	1216987	952123	986437	1589377	1698013	364699	357283	676807	398347	760549	927643	975343	1514413	1308247	1431379	858883	22000066
22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 22 embedded with four equal sums cocentric prime magic square of order 10. The prime magic square of order 20 is the same as given in Example 3.43.

Example 44. Block-wise Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																				22000066	
640009	859567	860089	741283	1543813	1247923	1271197	284023	712807	1382533	1456789	760993	719833	1005073	495337	262957	1158679	1443139	1660207	1570519	639259	1284037	22000066
1169017	1421317	1143193	1475137	535273	960493	367027	972649	1570729	554209	830989	1110643	760129	820627	834013	459463	1239739	1424869	736063	1356577	1368547	889363	22000066
441877	546739	544963	542947	1686409	300757	1690993	555523	1678429	1453267	1558129	667333	1164799	1134187	740023	1706743	1665583	271273	819769	662443	835207	1332673	22000066
1462603	592987	1733527	1582549	300109	1043899	1145359	928099	266479	1407019	537403	1524109	844183	485209	1362463	329083	1550449	1221247	536773	1514797	1155823	475897	22000066
1345777	851359	1074607	608977	953593	348739	1697677	1391029	925399	1148647	654229	1548847	1213183	1340929	1706539	1074847	733849	1191313	293467	659077	786823	451159	22000066
628423	711463	1355917	1463599	1744087	1000003	255919	536407	644089	1288543	1371583	506347	1370077	965407	285823	1116469	1000003	883537	1714183	1034599	629929	1493659	22000066
943543	541249	1588087	272983	302329	1651267	1046413	1727023	411919	1458757	1056463	870853	1369183	1002679	181957	808693	1266157	925159	1818049	997327	630823	1129153	22000066
1385023	1163257	381343	1071907	1699897	956107	854647	417457	1618663	836749	614983	1073383	716827	734047	1463233	1670923	449557	778759	637543	1265959	1283179	926623	22000066
982687	1725859	321577	1457059	313597	1699249	309013	1444483	1455043	274147	1017319	423127	930187	1337563	1259983	293263	334423	1728733	1180237	865819	1069819	1576879	22000066
1457857	1445797	856813	524869	1464733	1039513	1632979	1027357	429277	578689	542149	1798429	631459	1179379	1165993	1540543	760267	575137	1263943	643429	1239877	201577	22000066
543217	1140439	1139917	1258723	456193	752083	728809	1715983	1287199	617473	1359997	715969	1280173	994933	1504669	1737049	841327	556867	339799	429487	1360747	1239013	22000066
1941763	1050229	299569	1228657	862567	1683667	627799	722797	1480429	1025839	76717	676597	581983	801817	453367	1647649	341953	1090597	1386643	1029937	1644283	1345207	22000066
382267	1150879	1193737	736027	1659373	321403	1501483	844069	767317	825739	1617739	1148593	435847	757903	1530853	1093663	975847	323137	1049827	1288423	1544527	851413	22000066
1007317	986239	1943197	1451053	374299	1032007	843079	1193869	162517	1013767	992689	1444897	1279753	795727	862777	1481143	1271059	361909	1117273	1110133	720253	555109	22000066
271603	755809	597643	1790263	1428529	403867	1303069	74287	1402363	1244197	1728403	793327	623563	1119949	1151047	464539	1264933	1121833	997663	880057	1376443	1206679	22000066
1309249	1149979	1223449	537067	1392943	250147	1356919	1462939	776557	850027	690757	1146529	1634167	1129897	491299	888793	465679	1645537	1508707	870109	365839	853477	22000066
546283	340897	407347	612679	963979	1000003	1036027	1387327	1592659	1659109	1453723	1456657	708559	846823	1287067	1756747	1000003	243259	712939	1153183	1291447	543349	22000066
1095313	1353487	889783	134287	643087	1749859	607063	1865719	1110223	646519	904693	536749	854929	1579969	1068259	354469	1534327	1111213	931747	420037	1145077	1463257	22000066
643969	458377	101113	1925719	571477	1596139	696937	209743	1898893	1541629	1356037	1125907	1405267	637783	1002343	1535467	735073	878173	848959	1362223	594739	874099	22000066
564097	1630093	1837489	548953	1625707	967999	1156927	806137	56809	369913	1435909	1678639	1602463	889873	1137229	518863	728947	1638097	882733	1204279	397543	321367	22000066
1314883	1174267	806269	1263979	340633	1678603	498523	1155937	1232689	849127	685123	337339	455479	1242103	469153	906343	1024159	1676869	950179	711583	1564159	1662667	22000066
1923289	949777	1700437	771349	1137439	316339	1372207	1277209	519577	974167	58243	654799	1418023	1198189	1546639	352357	1658053	909409	613363	970069	355723	1323409	22000066
22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066	22000066

It is **block-wise prime magic square** of order 22 composed of four equal sums concentric prime magic square of order 11.

Example 45. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

22	mgc																					11000000
289127	161753	239699	15671	287867	499679	412289	266153	66161	438953	126683	123203	126359	686339	967229	979949	826349	973151	989909	999431	999029	525017	11000000
496841	550757	119447	355799	73331	304631	376709	44519	69911	181439	250751	292427	967763	348353	971561	997961	852239	978821	996461	969929	297191	503159	11000000
77783	211811	199103	368939	382463	319811	87911	480587	467261	308051	423257	405047	472247	79601	849917	955313	979061	979211	999773	242447	788189	922217	11000000
335417	253823	247799	415697	422453	281993	198659	164987	154613	430427	147377	460337	357989	915623	969863	990323	915869	997589	176201	752201	746177	664583	11000000
21383	275921	255083	212183	799343	149867	64661	221603	23357	81233	145967	889937	901133	942749	774491	905453	976883	123323	787817	744917	724079	978617	11000000
302873	58229	341057	423209	54269	109001	192617	318161	246473	173429	133877	460829	836117	948581	996323	975083	609509	945731	576791	658943	941771	697127	11000000
149519	330689	362291	274019	352349	22643	124067	382763	251117	157841	421559	24419	982061	959723	783599	912851	977357	647651	725981	637709	669311	850481	11000000
182681	172259	354479	238991	113489	70997	19841	35801	71129	156089	167543	620657	997649	957701	993431	980159	929003	886511	761009	645521	827741	817319	11000000
428411	151703	299567	14723	266177	352511	157721	466073	881591	86783	124739	940271	457889	508727	533927	842279	647489	733823	985277	700433	848297	571589	11000000
109541	304553	31091	163847	30539	120299	364433	29201	149057	306191	65951	934049	693809	850943	970799	635567	879701	969461	836153	968909	695447	890459	11000000
48869	341597	89381	41513	2903	65921	447683	979373	194963	878651	799619	200381	121349	805037	20627	552317	934079	997097	958487	910619	658403	951131	11000000
91529	400523	282011	12413	277757	989939	804191	790379	349709	517901	808553	191447	482099	650291	209621	195809	10061	722243	987587	717989	599477	908471	11000000
222269	125201	441527	876077	982769	919823	997973	919067	933407	297257	325877	674123	702743	66593	80933	2027	80177	17231	123923	558473	874799	777731	11000000
993401	912083	867467	933209	812627	963701	998381	773537	491273	913217	875261	59729	542111	118409	226463	1619	36299	187373	66791	132533	87917	6599	11000000
829877	229127	926567	572927	782501	997793	998561	6569	928871	843911	832457	379343	2351	42299	964199	1439	2207	217499	427073	73433	770873	170123	11000000
951389	984119	556709	998633	705821	996881	87149	617237	748883	842159	578441	975581	17939	40277	216401	875933	3119	294179	1367	443291	15881	48611	11000000
994769	995747	997121	999239	942779	390491	807383	681839	753527	826571	866123	539171	163883	51419	3677	24917	890999	57221	761	2879	4253	5231	11000000
999863	999491	998681	999521	876677	850133	935339	778397	976643	918767	854033	110063	98867	57251	225509	94547	23117	200657	479	1319	509	137	11000000
999917	999749	992513	823799	577547	718007	801341	835013	845387	569573	852623	539663	642011	84377	30137	9677	84131	2411	584303	7487	251	83	11000000
999959	999809	757553	631061	617537	680189	912089	519413	532739	691949	576743	594953	527753	920399	150083	44687	20939	20789	227	800897	191	41	11000000
999599	702809	880553	644201	926669	695369	623291	955481	930089	818561	749249	707573	32237	651647	28439	2039	147761	21179	3539	30071	449243	401	11000000
474983	838247	760301	984329	712133	500321	587711	733847	933839	561047	873317	876797	873641	313661	32771	20051	173651	26849	10091	569	971	710873	11000000
11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000	11000000

It is **concentric single-layer bordered** prime magic square of order 22. The internal part of order 20 is the same as given above in the Example 3.42.

3.9 Prime Magic Squares of Order 23

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 23 with different representations.

Example 46. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

23	mgc																					45963499	
1563503	2388083	821999	147347	2774669	1807607	1885469	3187733	3286799	3134597	2727713	1439177	2079347	3749633	2456459	374729	1173947	3782309	1865267	471923	1268783	1116107	2460299	45963499
365357	1777891	1340221	2892811	1932563	2010653	2457383	1294639	1656367	2151943	1863731	2295473	2393189	1392323	2698181	2392067	1557823	2154487	2376139	1717337	1246379	2365073	3631469	45963499
973283	3118561	2003641	888721	2658353	2133533	1608713	2558287	1700983	843679	2713589	2184131	1654673	3160601	2160857	1161113	2847799	2029483	1211167	2423999	1776263	1128527	3023543	45963499
3293363	1114471	2667061	2229391	1809683	2256413	2334503	1250023	1745599	2107327	1975073	2072789	2504531	1929647	1623533	2929391	1682827	1904479	2501143	1187453	2306147	1835189	703463	45963499
1939439	1134769	2061187	2844271	1400923	2724229	2563867	1617743	1180733	2767913	2085943	1200499	3162277	1083689	2278301	2316107	1198361	1825163	2251517	1052327	2870717	2346137	2057387	45963499
1198727	3722911	2013409	303907	3392617	2229673	1066729	3005633	1855463	705293	3225907	2149573	1073239	3125117	1892699	660281	2811503	1758347	705191	3383537	2089727	795917	2798099	45963499
1747079	1182547	1965631	2892049	1895479	1735117	3058423	943013	2530193	2093183	1136869	3098647	2213203	1469291	1507097	2701709	1265177	1691531	2318333	1833317	1308737	3127127	2249747	45963499
3621083	1826137	2124601	2782939	1474961	1335641	2808761	1435277	1801781	2679449	1821871	1488343	2524309	1072937	2156897	1925507	1345051	2573071	2362981	1117463	2576669	2732027	375743	45963499
2486873	3201361	2244559	1287757	3206921	1873121	539321	3216341	1972169	727997	2647279	1944841	1242403	2571017	1718447	865877	3111631	2093701	1075771	3756617	2142053	527489	1509953	45963499
1332119	1706179	2364517	2662981	937481	2410601	2271281	1264889	2142557	2509061	1365373	2401339	2067811	1511387	1279997	2363957	1824421	1614331	2842351	1552079	1707437	3166643	2664707	45963499
1301849	1352209	2813497	2339011	2200943	1787129	2747831	1652359	1793761	2650987	1328279	2312201	1896677	1088917	2510971	1842469	1455197	1322921	2668553	1040813	2402921	2759027	2694977	45963499
3136037	3155041	2168239	1181437	2792189	2245301	1698413	3030997	2032369	1033741	2414117	1845719	1277321	2567671	1814119	1060567	3028913	1815557	602201	3785801	2067587	349373	860789	45963499
2794907	1997467	1522981	2984269	1742771	2703473	2289659	1413751	2270977	2412379	1794761	1379237	2363159	1785769	1117267	2539321	962561	2308193	2175917	1376147	1732253	3094361	1201919	45963499
314117	1097699	2341907	2275211	1452977	1895507	2387087	1418239	2403679	2507389	1690811	2010527	2231819	1624279	1407877	2835523	1740421	1507789	2813563	1351403	2121869	2851097	3682709	45963499
3049199	3082451	1904939	727427	2845967	1911857	977747	3198919	2109769	1020619	2518727	1977719	1436711	3167137	1955893	744649	3093733	2020591	947449	3607817	2108123	608429	947627	45963499
274739	1534667	1467971	2712179	1436627	1928207	2370737	1712149	1815859	2801299	1723619	1944911	2264627	1076263	2503909	2287507	1227619	2533393	2300761	1365149	2094377	2864843	3722087	45963499
3638057	411937	544723	812761	1340329	1311547	2496271	2747177	2579651	5118713	2898569	2687723	4491761	2110753	3666001	4641037	565427	708221	1045199	301073	635279	852521	358769	45963499
192497	990631	589807	188983	2871991	1716049	560107	5853383	3481847	1110311	4952543	3359351	1766159	6002881	3472597	942313	1252721	772949	293177	1147739	596291	44843	3804329	45963499
2317979	366853	634891	767677	935827	2120551	2091769	1844981	4384043	4216517	2226941	4030979	3820133	2304157	3279193	4834441	500699	837677	980471	340061	557303	891509	1678847	45963499
1988759	2175097	2532697	4485097	1111087	2644063	1882921	597659	687083	1224131	336307	498937	747427	529181	1361357	1032299	3018527	2697599	4778663	2720183	3291371	3614987	2008067	45963499
3985433	5374297	3064297	754297	2651191	1879357	1107523	1462763	836291	209819	938677	527557	116437	1477397	974279	471161	5258399	3498263	1738127	4103651	3208847	2314043	11393	45963499
2912573	1643497	3595897	3953497	1875793	1114651	2647627	448451	985499	1074923	307687	556177	718807	916259	587201	1419377	2217863	4298927	3977999	2802707	3126323	3697511	1084253	45963499
1536527	1608743	3174827	3849479	1222157	2189219	2111357	809093	710027	862229	1269113	2557649	1917479	247193	1540367	3622097	2822879	214517	2131559	3524903	2728043	2880719	2433323	45963499
45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499	45963499

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 23 embedded with a prime magic square of order 21 with **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3. The prime magic square of order 21 is the same as given in Example 3.33.

Example 47. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

23	mgc																				23000069		
1285429	1055347	1631059	637783	587533	1859233	1499059	17419	1652719	774919	645937	1745599	1652839	390289	1650637	1543393	776947	1338979	9349	1201633	576637	380797	86533	23000069
1379629	1579813	52009	1368187	759673	1848193	392143	1707073	507589	785347	1854703	169483	975823	1933123	24049	1042837	1548073	358903	1093033	1675117	122029	1202863	620377	23000069
63667	788377	1000003	1211629	632473	1000003	1367533	78277	1000003	1921729	121123	1000003	1878883	109717	1000003	1890289	544963	1000003	1455043	527749	1000003	1472257	1936339	23000069
405199	631819	1947997	420193	1607863	151813	1240333	1214659	1492417	292933	1024183	1830523	145303	957169	1975957	66883	906973	1641103	451933	797143	1877977	324889	1594807	23000069
1095229	950869	658447	1390693	757243	1549837	692929	995713	450487	1553809	946249	1914007	139753	1079173	652039	1268797	552793	1188619	1258597	886807	1719049	394153	904777	23000069
1917523	1439827	1000003	560179	935689	1000003	1064317	1558099	1000003	441907	193507	1000003	1806499	1189627	1000003	810379	1705807	1000003	294199	507349	1000003	1492657	82483	23000069
1999633	609313	1341559	1049137	1307077	450169	1242763	446197	1549519	1004293	1860253	85999	1053757	731209	1347967	920833	741409	811387	1447213	1605853	280957	1113199	373	23000069
1389727	602983	1299367	1097659	88897	1869529	1041583	1168639	1382527	448843	429007	1564699	1006303	912463	1225933	861613	864007	1845199	290803	1856059	25087	1118863	610279	23000069
790519	1494679	1000003	505327	1952689	1000003	47317	280207	1000003	1719799	1577299	1000003	422707	949153	1000003	1050853	426799	1000003	1573207	262807	1000003	1737199	1209487	23000069
1619677	902347	700639	1397023	958423	130477	1911109	1551163	617479	831367	993703	435307	1570999	1138393	774073	1087543	1709203	154807	1135999	881143	1974919	143947	380329	23000069
126859	588619	1020037	1391353	703033	1402309	894667	801469	441877	1756663	928813	440893	1630303	1706533	196837	1096639	1637863	544627	817519	1095433	1361287	543289	1873147	23000069
1945729	1802737	1000003	197269	1191637	1000003	808369	1955197	1000003	44809	1701493	1000003	298513	390109	1000003	1609897	179659	1000003	1820347	447859	1000003	1552147	54277	23000069
1705009	608653	979969	1411387	1105339	597697	1296973	243343	1558129	1198537	369703	1559113	1071193	903367	1803169	293473	1182487	1455379	362143	1456717	638719	904573	294997	23000069
632623	499363	1998943	501703	1478887	65929	1455193	459763	1404919	1135327	971197	301789	1727023	1373683	1117759	508567	788023	1363189	848797	1248979	1339207	411823	1367383	23000069
206623	1002343	1000003	997663	976309	1000003	1023697	1675567	1000003	324439	1755829	1000003	244177	134887	1000003	1865119	1060777	1000003	939229	162847	1000003	1837159	1793383	23000069
162553	1498303	1063	1500643	544813	1934077	521119	864679	595087	1540243	272983	1698217	1028809	1491439	882247	626323	1151209	636817	1211983	1588183	660799	751027	1837453	23000069
693529	1819339	254377	926293	781423	1788229	430357	353833	1471573	1174603	1471123	760477	768409	412333	1230547	1357129	888793	1257247	853969	679207	746869	1573933	1306477	23000069
396667	106957	1000003	1893049	648937	1000003	1351069	1820773	1000003	179233	297289	1000003	1702717	1944799	1000003	55207	965179	1000003	1034827	1894729	1000003	105277	1603339	23000069
274627	1073713	1745629	180667	1569649	211777	1218583	825403	528433	1646173	1231597	1239529	528883	642877	769459	1587673	1146037	742759	1111213	426073	1253137	1320799	1725379	23000069
1390729	912103	1340947	746959	1049773	1837477	112759	1110349	738457	1151203	1029859	174877	1795273	1253347	184609	1562053	643129	1117867	1239013	1906909	80527	1012573	609277	23000069
1069459	834859	1000003	1165147	62989	1000003	1937017	1040857	1000003	959149	1765417	1000003	234589	1308709	1000003	691297	1595887	1000003	404119	105667	1000003	1894339	930547	23000069
535957	1253047	659059	1087903	1887247	162529	950233	848803	1261549	889657	204733	1825129	970147	437953	1815397	746659	760993	882139	1356877	987433	1919479	93097	1464049	23000069
1913473	944659	368947	1362223	1412473	140773	500947	1982587	347287	1225087	1354069	254407	347167	1609717	349369	456613	1223059	661027	1990657	798373	1423369	1619209	714577	23000069
23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 23 embedded with a prime magic square of order 21 with **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 3. The prime magic square of order 21 is the same as given in Example 3.34.

Example 48. Block-Bordered Nested with Different Sums Blocks of Order 7. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

23	mgc																				216221321		
1823443	7334137	380041	3457513	2575723	1712707	2617957	2275633	5839363	5627491	7435867	6043393	3593701	5108557	10456981	18737821	18773233	18478477	18773101	18801823	18801691	18801631	18771037	216221321
9970621	9469777	9494077	9494767	9496687	9497647	9498067	9494917	8978377	9033967	9036997	9037477	9037687	9037867	9035707	9647767	9685267	9687697	9687787	9689377	9691147	9686407	8831233	216221321
10119163	9493417	9455497	9493117	9493357	9527017	9492397	9491137	9032197	9000907	9032017	9032167	9046897	9029497	9024397	9684967	9656167	9684607	9685057	9702877	9682327	9679447	8682691	216221321
10449403	9493507	9493087	9492697	9485737	9498397	9491467	9491047	9032857	9029707	9031927	9013327	9039637	9026887	9023737	9687367	9683137	9685387	9669997	9691237	9681277	9677047	8352451	216221321
10853377	9496177	9505087	9497977	9492277	9486577	9479467	9488377	9040417	9038467	9036007	9028297	9020587	9018127	9016177	9690097	9693037	9688057	9682207	9676357	9671377	9674317	7948477	216221321
9993121	9498547	9515557	9486157	9498817	9491857	9468997	9486007	9041377	9045307	9016957	9043267	9024667	9011287	9015217	9692047	9696607	9673177	9694417	9679027	9667807	9672367	8808733	216221321
9863647	9504877	9492157	9491437	9491197	9457537	9529057	9479677	9051967	9027097	9024577	9024427	9009697	9055687	9004627	9695197	9682087	9679807	9679357	9661537	9708247	9669217	8938207	216221321
9989737	9489637	9490477	9489787	9487867	9486907	9486487	9514777	9020887	9022627	9019597	9019117	9018907	9018727	9078217	9678007	9679147	9676717	9676627	9675037	9673267	9716647	8812117	216221321
10041667	9546007	9595147	9595237	9598597	9598807	9599467	9602737	9356317	9403327	9403357	9407407	9407767	9412717	9415597	9172087	9215497	9217237	9217657	9218557	9220117	9215827	8760187	216221321
10700023	9593677	9559597	9592567	9593407	9617617	9591097	9588037	9403237	9387607	9401467	9401767	9412687	9401107	9398617	9215317	9187957	9214687	9215047	9224947	9212347	9206677	8101831	216221321
10651981	9596317	9591157	9596557	9572137	9603877	9590557	9585397	9407317	9401377	9404737	9382207	9415837	9400477	9394537	9218047	9212887	9211957	9207097	9213937	9209107	9203947	8149873	216221321
10748527	9601057	9602407	9598177	9590857	9583537	9579307	9580657	9411877	9405547	9412027	9400927	9389827	9396307	9389977	9219247	9219277	9212977	9210997	9209017	9202717	9202747	8053327	216221321
10744093	9609247	9610507	9577837	9609577	9585157	9571207	9572467	9420487	9409357	9386017	9419647	9397117	9392497	9381367	9219907	9225217	9208057	9214897	9210037	9196777	9202087	8057761	216221321
10047133	9610717	9590617	9589147	9588307	9564097	9622117	9570997	9420997	9400747	9400387	9400087	9389167	9414247	9380857	9226207	9209647	9207307	9206947	9197047	9234037	9195787	8754721	216221321
9987001	9578977	9586567	9586477	9583117	9582907	9582247	9635707	9386257	9398527	9398497	9394447	9394087	9389137	9445537	9206167	9206497	9204757	9204337	9203437	9201877	9249907	8814853	216221321
10175023	9077857	9124057	9124777	9126787	9127537	9129607	9126907	9721927	9778297	9782137	9782917	9783187	9786277	9780157	9253207	9312547	9315247	9316687	9318157	9326287	9324907	8626831	216221321
10333333	9123787	9088297	9122257	9124117	9143437	9120127	9115507	9777577	9759247	9776167	9776257	9781747	9774367	9769537	9312067	9279367	9310597	9310927	9336697	9310297	9307087	8468521	216221321
10614607	9124327	9120367	9127777	9102547	9128617	9118927	9114967	9780367	9774397	9773767	9761617	9785287	9772717	9766747	9321517	9310507	9315637	9295327	9317767	9308647	9297637	8187247	216221321
10064617	9127627	9128827	9120487	9119647	9118807	9110467	9111667	9783667	9776407	9785077	9773557	9762037	9770707	9763447	9323617	9321937	9311707	9309577	9307447	9297217	9295537	8737237	216221321
10128817	9132577	9141577	9110677	9136747	9111517	9097717	9106717	9789937	9784987	9761827	9785497	9773347	9762127	9757177	9324247	9327217	9301387	9323827	9303517	9291937	9294907	8673037	216221321
10030057	9138967	9119167	9117037	9115177	9095857	9150997	9100327	9794467	9772747	9770947	9770857	9765367	9787867	9752647	9338137	9308857	9308557	9308227	9282457	9339787	9281017	8771797	216221321
8861113	9112387	9115237	9114517	9112507	9111757	9109687	9161437	9766957	9768817	9764977	9764197	9763927	9760837	9825187	9294247	9306607	9303907	9302467	9300997	9292867	9365947	9940741	216221321
30817	11467717	18421813	15344341	16226131	17089147	16183897	16526221	12962491	13174363	11365987	12758461	15208153	13693297	8344873	64033	28621	323377	28753	31	163	223	16978411	216221321
216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321	216221321

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 23 embedded with a prime magic square of order 21 with **different sums** prime magic squares of order 7. The prime magic square of order 21 is the same as given in Example 3.35.

Example 49. Block-Bordered Nested with Equal Sums Blocks of Order 7. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

23	mgc																					23000069	
922309	1709137	466723	460063	1897243	506263	613813	390499	1445713	409099	178393	788947	1162339	1923403	1401559	1837663	1269223	745273	1166527	985219	817039	392443	1511179	23000069
1789603	1603297	891643	500029	868123	753793	430699	1952437	1721593	854263	393997	552397	601747	884077	1991947	1585897	903607	958333	486433	769039	824833	1471879	210403	23000069
1451053	1383367	1500127	254257	651517	878377	1715737	616639	1548073	1080613	784153	778213	487717	1869319	451933	1044739	1483177	772159	560017	535219	1649443	955267	548953	23000069
1861267	267229	1297399	1004287	305029	1690693	702607	1732777	968959	1440259	987559	313567	1698883	559747	1031047	1375243	969637	1488793	721387	789829	1030369	624763	138739	23000069
1149859	1672453	1437097	1686409	1000003	313597	562909	327553	1125283	1323727	1711327	1000003	288679	676279	874723	1235419	1596319	301039	1000003	1698967	403687	764587	850147	23000069
1469407	358417	481123	309313	1694977	995719	1518883	1641589	798067	1024729	301123	1686439	1012447	975277	1201939	932839	600319	1210177	1278619	511213	1399687	1067167	530599	23000069
1943197	1667689	284269	1745749	1348489	1121629	499879	332317	829987	130687	1215853	1221793	1512289	919393	1170019	297757	350563	1227847	1439989	1464787	516829	1702249	56809	23000069
37	47569	1108363	1499977	1131883	1246213	1569307	396709	8059	1145743	1606009	1447609	1398259	1115929	278413	528127	1096399	1041673	1513573	1230967	1175173	414109	1999969	23000069
780649	1424749	868453	683863	631753	525157	974749	1891297	1708669	576967	919183	721219	622159	455527	1996297	1704343	868873	859849	770233	493573	670333	1632817	1219357	23000069
56473	1647949	1617739	350947	749083	496477	1785769	352057	895813	1209079	656119	807637	363037	1964143	1104193	939997	1551037	602047	288559	596179	1962193	1060009	1943533	23000069
53629	310663	1090003	1478083	349519	1172407	910003	1689343	1064179	927049	1176787	464419	1358803	1072957	935827	1341883	1161313	1094377	736699	1168933	838693	658123	1946377	23000069
1919767	754969	566173	694327	1000003	1305679	1433833	1245037	1544449	1258927	1182019	1000003	817987	741079	455557	527407	661099	1074559	1000003	925447	1338907	1472599	80239	23000069
783619	1498969	1511863	827599	1650487	521923	488143	501037	325219	1569097	641203	1535587	823219	430909	1674787	1073239	1588753	831073	1263307	905629	411253	926767	1216387	23000069
1133809	1254013	214237	1649059	1250923	1503529	382267	745993	1457983	35863	1343887	1192369	1636969	790927	542023	1045963	37813	1397959	1711447	1403827	448969	954043	866197	23000069
1543309	108709	1131553	1316143	1368253	1474849	1025257	575257	3709	1423039	1080823	1278787	1377847	1544479	291337	367189	1131133	1140157	1229773	1506433	1329673	295663	456697	23000069
1429633	1714957	970903	858883	761347	307669	526069	1860193	1655209	945367	373063	875923	874879	366397	1909183	1614409	814309	525979	924499	422557	830419	1867849	570373	23000069
270217	1329709	1621423	339649	612877	444187	1981879	670297	747427	829519	849097	685393	643927	1992079	1252579	1123093	1727023	822163	341623	311827	1797379	876913	1729789	23000069
163063	1629109	851839	1199923	599143	1200943	1148167	370897	1555717	1527529	1164607	876229	959173	472477	444289	304933	1296679	667687	806269	1526053	703327	1695073	1836943	23000069
637657	389083	1719493	1001023	1000003	998983	280513	1610923	436687	1037593	794569	1000003	1205437	962413	1563319	1560883	419953	1858369	1000003	141637	1580053	439123	1362349	23000069
1002109	989827	789133	799063	1400863	800083	1210873	1010179	1535539	1597447	1040833	1123777	835399	402559	464467	1064593	1353733	473953	1193737	1332319	646273	935413	997897	23000069
1872427	807523	18127	1660357	1387129	1555819	378583	1192483	978619	7927	1150909	1314613	1356079	1170487	1021387	1199953	202627	1177843	1658383	1688179	272983	800053	127579	23000069
278149	139813	1029103	1141123	1238659	1692337	1473937	285049	90823	1054639	1626943	1124083	1125127	1633609	344797	132157	1185697	1474027	1075507	1577449	1169587	385597	1721857	23000069
488827	290869	1533283	1539943	102763	1493743	1386193	1609507	554293	1590907	1821613	1211059	837667	76603	598447	162343	730783	1254733	833479	1014787	1182967	1607563	1077697	23000069
23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 23 embedded with a prime magic square of order 21 with **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 7. The prime magic square of order 21 is the same as given in Example 3.36.

Example 50. Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider a following prime magic square:

23	mgc																				23000069		
1865329	479023	65629	547453	373669	768409	556609	791317	764587	878167	455599	614179	154423	522787	1870717	1828243	1907527	1572679	1895263	1627237	1777717	1675579	7927	23000069
689869	1373473	611953	526087	568207	942013	411127	203947	643243	550489	215617	218437	156823	898753	1674559	1717567	1831447	1978507	1993039	1979683	1988263	516829	1310137	23000069
867079	69067	255349	811729	66883	441523	576553	286513	869203	994579	848227	154873	997933	991777	902137	1684489	1749229	1975627	1999273	1995913	1398247	1930939	1132927	23000069
970069	308587	889489	721207	584359	356509	920677	774853	423127	86287	516883	331693	131749	1795327	1889527	1966663	1912213	1998019	1998349	592609	1110517	1691419	1029937	23000069
664549	265813	259783	868867	1859323	208213	509653	164413	830419	1627	272719	111409	1953517	1640077	1421689	1997503	1998679	1999867	30937	1131139	1740223	1734193	1335457	23000069
556279	511963	195457	726589	746659	2953	63607	611587	519433	734887	327343	769807	215983	1890103	1978993	1997467	1971127	1916749	1253347	1273417	1804549	1488043	1443727	23000069
924727	385249	638263	734653	556849	230143	721843	501463	310789	4219	860323	906679	603283	1992637	1998943	1934887	1164967	1769863	1443157	1265353	1361743	1614757	1075279	23000069
342379	325219	453949	556537	598789	536059	754903	812167	586129	816037	972319	614527	579907	1225723	1898539	1494679	1245103	1463947	1401217	1443469	1546057	1674787	1657627	23000069
329143	363757	714487	20773	487897	76873	707467	986113	23893	372277	674299	348259	1985239	1738837	1857217	1013893	1292539	1923133	1512109	1979233	1285519	1636249	1670863	23000069
80713	293467	321367	330607	810427	418357	571069	93889	428797	1996237	569887	517003	1834969	81919	1571209	1906117	1428937	1581649	1189579	1669399	1678639	1706539	1919293	23000069
419803	399613	115663	75703	891559	429277	410953	614893	1873513	567649	999613	1004677	995719	1432357	126493	1385113	1589053	1570729	1108447	1924303	1884343	1600393	1580203	23000069
561559	593059	158449	64927	784219	1968829	357913	427417	1781407	444043	996109	1000003	1003897	1555963	218599	1572589	1642093	31177	1215787	1935079	1841557	1406947	1438447	23000069
365689	580033	882529	883783	756199	1864399	1677037	1834663	1478689	73999	1004287	995329	1000393	1926007	521317	165343	322969	135607	1243807	1116223	1117477	1419973	1634317	23000069
420367	610843	1798183	888109	714739	1445929	1126537	1934389	1270933	1918087	1430119	1483003	165037	3769	729073	65617	873469	554077	1285267	1111897	201823	1389163	1579639	23000069
518059	1914103	1805887	1803973	724729	1969153	1927963	1791169	142789	1627729	1325707	1651747	14767	261169	1976113	208837	72043	30853	1275277	196033	194119	85903	1481947	23000069
112927	1597873	1945597	1943437	125113	1999567	1909309	505327	1413877	1183969	1027687	1385479	1420099	774283	101467	1187839	90697	439	1874893	56569	54409	402133	1887079	23000069
1879723	1989049	1994227	1993759	1985587	1975243	835039	1498543	1689217	1995787	1139683	1093327	1396723	7369	1063	65119	1278163	24763	14419	6247	5779	10957	120283	23000069
1632637	1980409	1973143	1997293	1988887	83257	1936399	1388419	1480573	1265119	1672663	1230199	1784023	109903	21013	2539	28879	1997053	11119	2713	26863	19597	367369	23000069
1921363	1988689	1999969	1982437	1969069	1791793	1490353	1835593	1169587	1998379	1727287	1888597	46489	359929	578317	2503	1327	139	140683	17569	37	11317	78643	23000069
1945873	1997173	1996507	1407397	1415647	1643497	1079329	1225153	1576879	1913719	1483123	1668313	1868257	204679	110479	33343	87793	1987	1657	1278799	3499	2833	54133	23000069
1993477	1969447	601759	1188277	1933123	1558483	1423453	1713493	1130803	1005427	1151779	1845133	1002073	1008229	1097869	315517	250777	24379	733	4093	1744657	30559	6529	23000069
1946377	1483177	1388053	1473919	1431799	1057993	1588879	1796059	1356763	1449517	1784389	1781569	1843183	1101253	325447	282439	168559	21499	6967	20323	11743	626533	53629	23000069
1992079	1520983	1934377	1452553	1626337	1231597	1443397	1208689	1235419	1121839	1544407	1385827	1845583	1477219	129289	171763	92479	427327	104743	372769	222289	324427	134677	23000069
23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069	23000069

It is **concentric single-layer bordered** prime magic square of order 23. The internal part of order 21 is the same as given above in the Example 3.37.

4 Author’s Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

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